

Self-Made Algebraic Semi-Magic Squares of Order 11

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The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16767>

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

*This work brings **semi-magic** squares of order 11 for **reduced entries**. By **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less number of entries. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These **entries** are **non-sequential positive** and **negative numbers**. Sometimes, we call these kind of magic squares as **self-made**. It means that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of entries and choose the magic sum, we get a magic square. In some cases, there maybe **decimal** or **fractional** values of entries depending on the types of magic squares. Different kind of magic squares are used to bring these **self-made** magic squares. These are of type, **block-wise**, **cornered**, **single-digit bordered**, **double-digit bordered**, etc. In some cases, the idea of **magic rectangles** is also applied. In each case, the **magic rectangles** are considered with **equal width** and **length**. This work for the self-made algebraic magic squares order 11. This work is available online at above given link. For similar kind of work for different orders the readers are suggested to author's work given in references [30]-[45].*

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1 Introduction

This work brings **self-made algebraic semi-magic** squares of order 11. By **self-made** or **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less numbers of entries, where the magic square is complete in itself. Putting any integer values for these less entries, we shall get always a magic square. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more **sequential** numbers. These entries are **non-sequential positive** and/or **negative** numbers. In some cases, these may be **decimal** or **fractional** values depending on the way of choosing the entries. Sometime to avoid **decimal** or **fractional** entries we apply certain conditions. These conditions depends on the types of magic squares. The name **self-made** is not known in the literature of magic squares. It is being introduced for the first time. The work is based on different types of magic squares, such as, **pandiagonal, block-wise, cornered, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered**, etc. It is not necessary, but we worked with **magic rectangles** having equal width and length for the same category within a magic square. If we relax this condition, i.e., by considering only equality of width, still we have good results.

This work for the order 11 brings **magic, semi-magic** and **pandiagonal** magic squares. It is divided in three parts. The first part is on magic squares, the second part on **semi-magic** squares and the third part on **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 11. This part is on **semi-magic** squares of order 11. For the first part on **magic** squares refer [42]. For more details on these kind of work refer author’s previous works [30]-[45]. The table below give the quantities and references for each order.

Order	Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Pandiagonal Magic Squares	Total
3	1	1	0	2 [38]
4	2	0	2	4 [38]
5	2	1	3	6 [38]
6	5	1	6	12 [38]
7	5	3	8	16 [38]
8	8	5	13	26 [39]
9	10	9	18	28 [40]
10	15	14	29	58 [41]
11	25	23	to be done	48 [42, 43]
12	28	25	to be done	53 [44, 45]

The author [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] also worked similar kind of work but from different point of view. This work is for the magic squares of orders 3 to 12 for the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and **days** are the sums of the magic squares.

2 Magic Squares of Order 11

Below are three different examples of magic squares of order 11 for sequential entries from 1 to 121.

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										671
	58	63	62	54	68	43	79	87	35	13	109	671
	65	61	57	55	67	78	44	25	97	104	18	671
	60	59	64	72	50	75	47	24	98	8	114	671
	56	52	53	73	71	38	84	89	33	3	119	671
	66	70	69	51	49	39	83	92	30	106	16	671
	81	37	40	76	77	74	42	29	93	5	117	671
	41	85	82	46	45	80	48	23	99	105	17	671
	21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671
	101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671
	120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671
	2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
	121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	671
	119	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	3	671
	117	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	5	671
	115	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	7	671
	11	93	79	51	59	61	63	71	43	29	111	671
	13	91	77	66	64	57	62	56	45	31	109	671
	15	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	107	671
	17	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	105	671
	19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	671
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										671
	112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671
	10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671
	100	22	85	79	42	55	44	50	72	94	28	671
	8	114	37	43	80	67	78	40	82	31	91	671
	107	15	49	73	62	63	58	76	46	24	98	671
	96	26	38	84	57	61	65	70	52	111	11	671
	35	87	66	56	64	59	60	69	53	25	97	671
	104	18	71	51	83	75	45	48	54	19	103	671
	6	116	81	41	39	47	77	74	68	120	2	671
	4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671
	89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

The first example is known by **cornered** magic squares. The second example is famous as **single-digit bordered** magic square. The third example is known as **double-digit bordered** magic square. For more details on these kind of magic squares refer author's work [24, 25, 26, 27].

2.1 Self-Made Semi-Magic Squares of order 11

Below are 23 examples of **self-made semi-magic** squares for **reduced entries**. In order to bring them as **magic squares** we shall use some conditions. These conditions are given below:

$$R := \frac{11}{9} \times L \tag{1}$$

$$L := \frac{9}{7} \times T \tag{2}$$

$$T := \frac{7}{5} \times S \tag{3}$$

$$S := \frac{5}{3} \times M \tag{4}$$

where the letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic or semi-magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11.

Result 2.1. Let's consider following **self-made semi-magic** square of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(R-T)/2-A26$	A28	$A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A42$	$(R-T)/2-A43$	$(R-T)/2-A44$	$(R-T)/2-A45$	$(R-T)/2-A46$	$(R-T)/2-A47$	$2*R-A48-A27-9*(R-T)/2-A28$	$A26-R+9*(R-T)/4+A27+A48$
A27	A26	$7*(R-T)/4-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47$	A42	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	$R-A48-A26-A27-7*(R-T)/4$	A48
$A20+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25-5*(R-T)/4$	$7*(R-T)/4-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25$	A17	$T-S+A10+A14-A13$	A10	$S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13$	A11	A12	A18	$7*(R-T)/4-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40$	$A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40-5*(R-T)/4$
$(R-T)/2-A20$	A20	A14	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4$	A3	A4	$T-S-A14$	A35	$(R-T)/2-A35$
$(R-T)/2-A21$	A21	$5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13$	$A8-A2+A7$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	$S-A1-A3-A4-A8$	$5*S-4*T+A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17$	A36	$(R-T)/2-A36$
$(R-T)/2-A22$	A22	A15	$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8$	A7	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A8$	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	$T-S-A15$	A37	$(R-T)/2-A37$
$(R-T)/2-A23$	A23	A16	$A7-A3+A5$	$A1-A6+A8$	$A2+A3-A7$	$S-A1-A5-A7-A8$	$A7-A2+A6$	$T-S-A16$	A38	$(R-T)/2-A38$
$(R-T)/2-A24$	A24	A13	$S-A1-A4-A7-A8$	$A3+A4-A5$	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A6$	A8	$T-S-A13$	A39	$(R-T)/2-A39$
$(R-T)/2-A25$	A25	$6*S-A18-4*T$	$A13-A10-A14$	$T-S-A10$	$A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10+T-2*S+A14-A13$	$T-S-A11$	$T-S-A12$	$T-S-A17$	A40	$(R-T)/2-A40$
$A26+A48-A41$	$(7*R-11*T)/4+A27+A48-A41$	$7*(R-T)/4-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34$	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A41	$A41-A26-(5*R-9*T)/2-A27-2*A48$
$A41+R-9*(R-T)/4-A27-A48$	$(9*T-5*R)/2-A28-A27-A26-A48+A41$	$A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A29$	$(R-T)/2-A30$	$(R-T)/2-A31$	$(R-T)/2-A32$	$(R-T)/2-A33$	$(R-T)/2-A34$	$A28+(5*R-9*T)/2+2*A27+A26+2*A48-A41$	$(R-T)/2-A41$

• **Details:**

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 having **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 are of equal width and length. The letters S, T and R represents the magic squares of orders 5, 7 and 11 respectively. The difference between R and T should be multiple of 4 to avoid **decimal** entries. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (3), i.e., $T := \frac{7}{5} \times S$. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.1. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.1:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-295
-76	92	824	-124	-127	-130	-133	-136	-139	-103	212	160	
89	86	-814	134	137	140	143	146	149	-202	152	160	
428	-418	59	146	38	-250	41	44	62	-688	698	160	
-58	68	50	11	14	-27	17	20	55	113	-103	160	
-61	71	287	47	23	-16	26	-45	-182	116	-106	160	
-64	74	53	-1	-33	29	53	-13	52	119	-109	160	
-67	77	56	35	17	2	-60	41	49	122	-112	160	
-70	80	47	-57	14	47	-1	32	58	125	-115	160	
-73	83	-412	-41	67	355	64	61	46	128	-118	160	
107	5	-580	95	98	101	104	107	110	131	-118	160	
5	-58	590	-85	-88	-91	-94	-97	-100	299	-121	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

The **semi-magic** square given in Example 2.1 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

7	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							-315						
59	146	38	-250	41	44	62	140	5	pan	35	35	35	35	35	
50	11	14	-27	17	20	55	140	35	11	14	-27	17	20	35	
287	47	23	-16	26	-45	-182	140	35	47	23	-16	26	-45	35	
53	-1	-33	29	53	-13	52	140	35	-1	-33	29	53	-13	35	
56	35	17	2	-60	41	49	140	35	35	17	2	-60	41	35	
47	-57	14	47	-1	32	58	140		-57	14	47	-1	32	35	
-412	-41	67	355	64	61	46	140		35	35	35	35	35	35	
140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140								

Example 2.2. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.1:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
	-58	92	779	-106	-109	-112	-115	-118	-121	-249	285	168
	89	86	-751	134	137	140	143	146	149	-257	152	168
	383	-355	59	73	38	-205	41	44	62	-625	653	168
	-40	68	50	11	14	18	17	20	-18	113	-85	168
	-43	71	-123	47	23	-16	26	0	155	116	-88	168
	-46	74	53	-1	12	29	53	-13	-21	119	-91	168
	-49	77	56	35	17	2	-15	41	-24	122	-94	168
	-52	80	47	-12	14	47	-1	32	-15	125	-97	168
	-55	83	-30	-41	-6	237	-9	-12	-27	128	-100	168
	107	96	-517	95	98	101	104	107	110	131	-264	168
	-68	-204	545	-67	-70	-73	-76	-79	-82	445	-103	168
	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168

It includes the following magic squares:

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							112								
	59	73	38	-205	41	44	62	112	5	pan	80	80	80	80	80	80	80
	50	11	14	18	17	20	-18	112	80	11	14	18	17	20	80	80	80
	-123	47	23	-16	26	0	155	112	80	47	23	-16	26	0	80	80	80
	53	-1	12	29	53	-13	-21	112	80	-1	12	29	53	-13	80	80	80
	56	35	17	2	-15	41	-24	112	80	35	17	2	-15	41	80	80	80
	47	-12	14	47	-1	32	-15	112		-12	14	47	-1	32	80	80	80
	-30	-41	-6	237	-9	-12	-27	112		80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80
	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112									

Result 2.2. Let's consider following **self-made semi-magic** square of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(A47-A17)/2-A24$	A26	$A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45-5*(A47-A17)/4$	$(A47-A17)/2-A40$	$(A47-A17)/2-A41$	$(A47-A17)/2-A42$	$(A47-A17)/2-A43$	$(A47-A17)/2-A44$	$(A47-A17)/2-A45$	$2*A47-A46-A25-9*(A47-A17)/2-A26$	$A24-A47+9*(A47-A17)/4+A25+A46$
A25	A24	$7*(A47-A17)/4-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45$	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	$A47-A46-A24-A25-7*(A47-A17)/4$	A46
$A18+A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-5*(A47-A17)/4$	$7*(A47-A17)/4-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23$	A15	$(7/2)*A17-(9/2)*A7-A8+A5-2*A3-A11$	A8	$(9/2)*A7-A15-A16-A10-A9-A5+2*A3-(5/2)*A17+A11$	A9	A10	A16	$7*(A47-A17)/4-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38$	$A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38-5*(A47-A17)/4$
$(A47-A17)/2-A18$	A18	$(5/2)*A17-(5/2)*A7-A15+A16-A14+2*A8-A5+2*A3-A13-A11$	$A1+A2-A3/3$	$2*A3/3-A2$	$2*A3/3-A1$	$3*(A7-A3)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(A7-A3)/2$	$(3/2)*A7-(3/2)*A17+A11-2*A8+A5-2*A3+A13+A14-A16+A15$	A33	$(A47-A17)/2-A33$
$(A47-A17)/2-A19$	A19	$A5-(7/2)*A7-2*A3+(5/2)*A17-2*A8$	$4*A3/3-2*A1-A2$	A3/3	$2*A1+A2-2*A3/3$	A5	A7-A3-A5	$(5/2)*A7-(3/2)*A17+2*A8-A5+2*A3$	A34	$(A47-A17)/2-A34$
$(A47-A17)/2-A20$	A20	A13	A1	A2	A3-A1-A2	A6	A7-A3-A6	A17-A7-A13	A35	$(A47-A17)/2-A35$
$(A47-A17)/2-A21$	A21	A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(A7-A3)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(A7-A3)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(A7-A3)/2$	$2*A3-A7$	A17-A7-A14	A36	$(A47-A17)/2-A36$
$(A47-A17)/2-A22$	A22	A11	$A1+3*(A7-A3)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	A7-A3-A4	$2*A4-A7+A3-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*A3-A7$	$(A7-A3)/2$	A17-A7-A11	A37	$(A47-A17)/2-A37$
$(A47-A17)/2-A23$	A23	$6*A7-A16-4*A17$	$A11+A8-A5+(7/2)*A7+2*A3-(5/2)*A17$	A17-A7-A8	$A15+A16+A10+A9+(7/2)*A17-(11/2)*A7+A5-2*A3-A11$	A17-A7-A9	A17-A7-A10	A17-A7-A15	A38	$(A47-A17)/2-A38$
$A24+A46-A39$	$(7*A47-11*A17)/4+A25+A46-A39$	$7*(A47-A17)/4-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32$	A27	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A39	$A39-A24-(5*A47-9*A17)/2-A25-2*A46$
$A39+A47-9*(A47-A17)/4-A25-A46$	$(9*A17-5*A47)/2-A26-A25-A24-A46+A39$	$A27+A28+A29+A30+A31+A32-5*(A47-A17)/4$	$(A47-A17)/2-A27$	$(A47-A17)/2-A28$	$(A47-A17)/2-A29$	$(A47-A17)/2-A30$	$(A47-A17)/2-A31$	$(A47-A17)/2-A32$	$A26+(5*A47-9*A17)/2+2*A25+A24+2*A46-A39$	$(A47-A17)/2-A39$

• **Details:**

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7. It again contains a **cornered** magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×7 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (3), i.e., $T := \frac{7}{5} \times S$. Moreover the magic square of order 3 should be multiple of 3 to avoid **decimal** entries. Also the difference between R and T should be multiple of 4. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.3. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.2:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-168
-50	86	738	-98	-101	-104	-107	-110	-113	-225	264	180	
83	80	-708	128	131	134	137	140	143	-234	146	180	
342	-312	53	172	32	-266	35	38	56	-582	612	180	
-32	62	152	19	-2	1	-22	40	-68	107	-77	180	
-35	65	97	-12	6	24	23	-5	-13	110	-80	180	
-38	68	47	11	14	-7	26	-8	37	113	-83	180	
-41	71	50	58	20	-51	9	0	34	116	-86	180	
-44	74	41	-40	-2	69	0	9	43	119	-89	180	
-47	77	-320	-88	52	350	49	46	31	122	-92	180	
101	89	-474	89	92	95	98	101	104	125	-240	180	
-59	-180	504	-59	-62	-65	-68	-71	-74	409	-95	180	
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

The **semi-magic** square given in Example 2.3 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

7	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							-228												
53	172	32	-266	35	38	56	120	5	mgc						36						
152	19	-2	1	-22	40	-68	120			19	-2	1	-22	40	36	3	mgc		18		
97	-12	6	24	23	-5	-13	120			-12	6	24	23	-5	36			19	-2	1	18
47	11	14	-7	26	-8	37	120			11	14	-7	26	-8	36			-12	6	24	18
50	58	20	-51	9	0	34	120			58	20	-51	9	0	36			11	14	-7	18
41	-40	-2	69	0	9	43	120			-40	-2	69	0	9	36			18	18	18	18
-320	-88	52	350	49	46	31	120			36	36	36	36	36	36						
120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120														

Example 2.4. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.2:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										190
-48	86	733	-96	-99	-102	-105	-108	-111	-223	263	190	
83	80	-701	128	131	134	137	140	143	-231	146	190	
337	-305	53	-86	32	-2	35	38	56	-575	607	190	
-30	62	68	13	10	13	32	22	-32	107	-75	190	
-33	65	-113	12	12	12	23	31	149	110	-78	190	
-36	68	47	11	14	11	26	28	-11	113	-81	190	
-39	71	50	40	20	21	27	-18	-14	116	-84	190	
-42	74	41	14	34	33	-18	27	-5	119	-87	190	
-45	77	-20	122	4	38	1	-2	-17	122	-90	190	
101	90	-467	89	92	95	98	101	104	125	-238	190	
-58	-178	499	-57	-60	-63	-66	-69	-72	407	-93	190	
190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	190	

It includes the following magic squares:

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						126
53	-86	32	-2	35	38	56	126	
68	13	10	13	32	22	-32	126	
-113	12	12	12	23	31	149	126	
47	11	14	11	26	28	-11	126	
50	40	20	21	27	-18	-14	126	
41	14	34	33	-18	27	-5	126	
-20	122	4	38	1	-2	-17	126	
126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	

5	mgc						90
13	10	13	32	22		90	
12	12	12	23	31		90	
11	14	11	26	28		90	
40	20	21	27	-18		90	
14	34	33	-18	27		90	
90	90	90	90	90		90	

3	mgc				36
13	10	13		36	
12	12	12		36	
11	14	11		36	
36	36	36		36	

Result 2.3. Let's consider following **self-made semi-magic** square of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(R-T)/2-A27$	A29	$A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A43$	$(R-T)/2-A44$	$(R-T)/2-A45$	$(R-T)/2-A46$	$(R-T)/2-A47$	$(R-T)/2-A48$	$2*R-A49-A28-9*(R-T)/2-A29$	$A27-R+9*(R-T)/4+A28+A49$
A28	A27	$7*(R-T)/4-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48$	A43	A44	A45	A46	A47	A48	$R-A49-A27-A28-7*(R-T)/4$	A49
$A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26-5*(R-T)/4$	$7*(R-T)/4-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	A18	$T-S+A11+A15-A14$	A11	$S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14$	A12	A13	A19	$7*(R-T)/4-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41$	$A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41-5*(R-T)/4$
$(R-T)/2-A21$	A21	$5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14$	A6	$M-A6-A9-A8+A7$	$S-M-A7$	A8	A9	$5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18$	A36	$(R-T)/2-A36$
$(R-T)/2-A22$	A22	A15	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6$	$T-S-A15$	A37	$(R-T)/2-A37$
$(R-T)/2-A23$	A23	A16	A5	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	$M/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	$S-M-A5$	$T-S-A16$	A38	$(R-T)/2-A38$
$(R-T)/2-A24$	A24	A17	A4	A1	A2	$M-A1-A2$	$S-M-A4$	$T-S-A17$	A39	$(R-T)/2-A39$
$(R-T)/2-A25$	A25	A14	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	$S-M-A8$	$S-M-A6$	$T-S-A14$	A40	$(R-T)/2-A40$
$(R-T)/2-A26$	A26	$6*S-A19-4*T$	$A14-A11-A15$	$T-S-A11$	$A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14$	$T-S-A12$	$T-S-A13$	$T-S-A18$	A41	$(R-T)/2-A41$
$A27+A49-A42$	$(7*R-11*T)/4+A28+A49-A42$	$7*(R-T)/4-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35$	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A42	$A42-A27-(5*R-9*T)/2-A28-2*A49$
$A42+R-9*(R-T)/4-A28-A49$	$(9*T-5*R)/2-A29-A28-A27-A49+A42$	$A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A30$	$(R-T)/2-A31$	$(R-T)/2-A32$	$(R-T)/2-A33$	$(R-T)/2-A34$	$(R-T)/2-A35$	$A29+(5*R-9*T)/2+2*A28+A27+2*A49-A42$	$(R-T)/2-A42$

• **Details:**

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **single-digit bordered** magic squares of order 7 and 5 having magic square of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal width and length. The letters M, S, T and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the conditions given in (3) and (4), i.e., $T := \frac{7}{5} \times S$ and $S := \frac{5}{3} \times M$. Moreover the magic square of order 3 should be multiple of 3 to avoid **decimal** entries. Also the difference between R and T should be multiple of 4. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.5. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.3:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-90
-58	94	786	-106	-109	-112	-115	-118	-121	-265	296	172	
91	88	-756	136	139	142	145	148	151	-266	154	172	
390	-360	61	103	40	-245	43	46	64	-630	660	172	
-40	70	37	25	-44	6	31	34	23	115	-85	172	
-43	73	52	52	17	-1	2	-18	8	118	-88	172	
-46	76	55	22	-9	6	21	12	5	121	-91	172	
-49	79	58	19	10	13	-5	15	2	124	-94	172	
-52	82	49	-66	78	28	3	9	11	127	-97	172	
-55	85	-200	-43	20	305	17	14	-1	130	-100	172	
109	105	-522	97	100	103	106	109	112	133	-280	172	
-75	-220	552	-67	-70	-73	-76	-79	-82	465	-103	172	
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	

The magic square given in Example 2.5 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

7	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						-150											
61	103	40	-245	43	46	64	112	5	semi						-14				
37	25	-44	6	31	34	23	112		25	-44	6	31	34	52	3	mgc	18		
52	52	17	-1	2	-18	8	112		52	17	-1	2	-18	52		17	-1	2	18
55	22	-9	6	21	12	5	112		22	-9	6	21	12	52		-9	6	21	18
58	19	10	13	-5	15	2	112		19	10	13	-5	15	52		10	13	-5	18
49	-66	78	28	3	9	11	112		-66	78	28	3	9	52		18	18	18	18
-200	-43	20	305	17	14	-1	112		52	52	52	52	52	52					
112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112												

Example 2.6. Let's consider an example of *magic* square of order 11 based on the Result 2.3:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										121	
		-66	94	806	-114	-117	-120	-123	-126	-129	-295	311	121
		91	88	-784	136	139	142	145	148	151	-289	154	121
		410	-388	61	65	40	-242	43	46	64	-658	680	121
		-48	70	-156	25	-29	-6	31	34	178	115	-93	121
		-51	73	52	1	12	9	12	21	-30	118	-96	121
		-54	76	55	22	11	11	11	0	-33	121	-99	121
		-57	79	58	19	10	13	10	3	-36	124	-102	121
		-60	82	49	-12	51	28	-9	-3	-27	127	-105	121
		-63	85	-42	-43	-18	264	-21	-24	-39	130	-108	121
		109	112	-550	97	100	103	106	109	112	133	-310	121
		-90	-250	572	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-90	495	-111	121
		121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121

The above Example 2.6 is obtained by applying the conditions $T := \frac{7}{5} \times S$ and $S := \frac{5}{3} \times M$. It includes the following magic squares:

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							77						
		61	65	40	-242	43	46	64	77						
		-156	25	-29	-6	31	34	178	77						
		52	1	12	9	12	21	-30	77						
		55	22	11	11	11	0	-33	77						
		58	19	10	13	10	3	-36	77						
		49	-12	51	28	-9	-3	-27	77						
		-42	-43	-18	264	-21	-24	-39	77						
		77	77	77	77	77	77	77	77						

5	mgc						55
		25	-29	-6	31	34	55
		1	12	9	12	21	55
		22	11	11	11	0	55
		19	10	13	10	3	55
		-12	51	28	-9	-3	55
		55	55	55	55	55	55

3	mgc				33
		12	9	12	33
		11	11	11	33
		10	13	10	33
		33	33	33	33

Result 2.4. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

R-L-A49	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	L+A49-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40
R-L-A41	$(L-S)/2-A28$	A29	$A20+A21+A22+A23-2*(L-S)$	$(L-S)/2-A20$	$(L-S)/2-A21$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(L-S)/2-A23$	$(7*S-3*L)/2-A14-A19-A29$	$A28+2*L-3*S+A14+A19$	A41
R-L-A42	A30	A28	$5*(L-S)/2-A20-A21-A22-A23$	A20	A21	A22	A23	$(5*S-3*L)/2-A28-A14-A19$	$A14+A19-A30$	A42
R-L-A43	$A24+A25+A26+A27-2*(L-S)$	$5*(L-S)/2-A24-A25-A26-A27$	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	$5*(L-S)/2-A15-A16-A17-A18$	$A15+A16+A17+A18-2*(L-S)$	A43
R-L-A44	$(L-S)/2-A24$	A24	$A8-A2+A7$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A15	$(L-S)/2-A15$	A44
R-L-A45	$(L-S)/2-A25$	A25	$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	S-A1-A2-A3-A4-A6-A8	A7	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A8$	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$	A45
R-L-A46	$(L-S)/2-A26$	A26	$A7-A3+A5$	$A1-A6+A8$	$A2+A3-A7$	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	$A7-A2+A6$	A17	$(L-S)/2-A17$	A46
R-L-A47	$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	$A3+A4-A5$	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A6$	A8	A18	$(L-S)/2-A18$	A47
R-L-A48	$(7*S-3*L)/2-A14-A30-A29$	$(5*S-3*L)/2-A14-A28-A29$	$5*(L-S)/2-A10-A11-A12-A13$	A10	A11	A12	A13	$(3*L-7*S)/2+A28+2*A14+A19+A29$	$A29-A19+A30$	A48
$2*A49-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48$	$2*L-3*S+A28+A14+A29$	A14	$A10+A11+A12+A13-2*(L-S)$	$(L-S)/2-A10$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(L-S)/2-A13$	A19	$3*S-L-A28-2*A14-A19-A29$	$R-L-2*A49+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48$
$9*L-8*R+A34+A33+A32-A49+A38+A37+A36+A35+A40+A39$	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	A49

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **double-digit bordered** magic squares of order 9 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in the middle. The magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal width and length. The letters S, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 5, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. To avoid decimal entries the difference between R and L should be multiple of 2. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.7. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.4:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-156	
		-97	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	-781	157
		-73	-58	94	154	-34	-37	-40	-43	-238	302	130	157
		-76	97	91	-121	67	70	73	76	-269	16	133	157
		-79	202	-169	10	13	-24	16	19	-61	94	136	157
		-82	-46	79	46	22	-17	25	-42	52	-19	139	157
		-85	-49	82	-2	-30	28	52	-14	55	-22	142	157
		-88	-52	85	34	16	1	-57	40	58	-25	145	157
		-91	-55	88	-54	13	46	-2	31	61	-28	148	157
		-94	-271	-299	-1	37	40	43	46	378	127	151	157
		397	332	49	34	-4	-7	-10	-13	64	-345	-340	157
		525	-46	-49	-52	-55	-58	-61	-64	-67	-70	154	157
		157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157

The **semi-magic** square given in Example 2.7 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									100
		-58	94	154	-34	-37	-40	-43	-238	302	100
		97	91	-121	67	70	73	76	-269	16	100
		202	-169	10	13	-24	16	19	-61	94	100
		-46	79	46	22	-17	25	-42	52	-19	100
		-49	82	-2	-30	28	52	-14	55	-22	100
		-52	85	34	16	1	-57	40	58	-25	100
		-55	88	-54	13	46	-2	31	61	-28	100
		-271	-299	-1	37	40	43	46	378	127	100
		332	49	34	-4	-7	-10	-13	64	-345	100
		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

5	pan	34	34	34	34	34		
		34	10	13	-24	16	19	34
		34	46	22	-17	25	-42	34
		34	-2	-30	28	52	-14	34
		34	34	16	1	-57	40	34
			-54	13	46	-2	31	34
			34	34	34	34	34	34

Example 2.8. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.4:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										132	
		-130	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	-773	132
		-106	-54	94	138	-30	-33	-36	-39	-250	318	130	132
		-109	97	91	-101	67	70	73	76	-281	16	133	132
		-112	186	-149	10	13	-24	16	19	-41	78	136	132
		-115	-42	79	46	22	-17	25	-42	52	-15	139	132
		-118	-45	82	-2	-30	28	52	-14	55	-18	142	132
		-121	-48	85	34	16	1	-57	40	58	-21	145	132
		-124	-51	88	-54	13	46	-2	31	61	-24	148	132
		-127	-283	-311	19	37	40	43	46	390	127	151	132
		397	348	49	18	0	-3	-6	-9	64	-353	-373	132
		797	-79	-82	-85	-88	-91	-94	-97	-100	-103	154	132
		132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132

The above Example 2.8 is obtained by applying the condition $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										108	
		-54	94	138	-30	-33	-36	-39	-250	318			108
		97	91	-101	67	70	73	76	-281	16			108
		186	-149	10	13	-24	16	19	-41	78			108
		-42	79	46	22	-17	25	-42	52	-15			108
		-45	82	-2	-30	28	52	-14	55	-18			108
		-48	85	34	16	1	-57	40	58	-21			108
		-51	88	-54	13	46	-2	31	61	-24			108
		-283	-311	19	37	40	43	46	390	127			108
		348	49	18	0	-3	-6	-9	64	-353			108
		108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108			108

5	pan	34	34	34	34	34	
34		10	13	-24	16	19	34
34		46	22	-17	25	-42	34
34		-2	-30	28	52	-14	34
34		34	16	1	-57	40	34
		-54	13	46	-2	31	34
		34	34	34	34	34	34

Result 2.5. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

R-L-A47	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	L+A47-A30-A31- A32-A33-A34-A35- A36-A37-A38
R-L-A39	$(S-L)/2+A28+2*A12+A17-A18$	A28	$3*(S-L)/4+A19+A20+A21+A22$	$(L-S)/2-A19$	$(L-S)/2-A20$	$(L-S)/2-A21$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(5*S-L)/4-A28-A12-A17$	$(L-S)/2-A28-A12+A18$	A39
R-L-A40	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A17-A23+A12$	$L-S-A28-2*A12-A17+A18$	$5*(L-S)/4-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A19	A20	A21	A22	A28+A12-A18	A23	A40
R-L-A41	$3*(S-L)/4+A24+A25+A26+A27$	$5*(L-S)/4-A24-A25-A26-A27$	$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$5*(L-S)/4-A13-A14-A15-A16$	$3*(S-L)/4+A13+A14+A15+A16$	A41
R-L-A42	$(L-S)/2-A24$	A24	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	$M/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A13	$(L-S)/2-A13$	A42
R-L-A43	$(L-S)/2-A25$	A25	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A14	$(L-S)/2-A14$	A43
R-L-A44	$(L-S)/2-A26$	A26	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	$(S-M)/2$	$2*M-S$	A15	$(L-S)/2-A15$	A44
R-L-A45	$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	$2*M-S$	$(S-M)/2$	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$	A45
R-L-A46	$L-S-A28-2*A12+A18-2*A17+A23$	A12	$5*(L-S)/4-A8-A9-A10-A11$	A8	A9	A10	A11	A17	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A28+A12-A18+A17-A23$	A46
$2*A47-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46$	$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A12+A17-A18$	$3*(S-L)/4+A8+A9+A10+A11$	$(L-S)/2-A8$	$(L-S)/2-A9$	$(L-S)/2-A10$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	A18	$(L-S)/2-A17$	R-L-2*A47 +A30+A31+A32+ A33+A34+A35+A 36+A37+A38-A39- A40-A41-A42-A43- A44-A45-A46
$9*L-8*R+A32+A31+A30-A47+A36+A35+A34+A33+A38+A37$	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	A47

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **double-digit bordered** magic squares of order 9 having a **cornered** magic square of order 5 in the middle. It contains magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×3 and 2×5 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. To avoid decimal entries the difference between S and L should be multiple of 4. Moreover, the magic square of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.9. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.5:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154
	-120	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	-707	154
	-96	138	91	220	-28	-31	-34	-37	-156	-37	124	154
	-99	-11	-102	-184	64	67	70	73	73	76	127	154
	-102	280	-244	13	7	10	-11	35	-112	148	130	154
	-105	-43	79	7	10	13	22	2	46	-10	133	154
	-108	-46	82	10	13	7	25	-1	49	-13	136	154
	-111	-49	85	53	19	-36	12	6	52	-16	139	154
	-114	-52	88	-29	5	60	6	12	55	-19	142	154
	-117	-84	43	-52	31	34	37	40	58	19	145	154
	391	-7	4	88	5	2	-1	-4	61	-22	-363	154
	735	-69	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-90	-93	148	154
	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

The magic square given in Example 2.9 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								120
	136	91	217	-26	-29	-32	-35	-167	-35	120
	-26	-98	-179	64	67	70	73	73	76	120
	277	-239	15	3	6	-17	37	-107	145	120
	-41	79	-1	8	17	22	-2	46	-8	120
	-44	82	10	13	1	25	-5	49	-11	120
	-47	85	55	19	-44	10	4	52	-14	120
	-50	88	-35	1	64	4	10	55	-17	120
	-80	43	-47	31	34	37	40	58	4	120
	-5	-11	85	7	4	1	-2	61	-20	120
	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

5	mgc						44
	15	3	6	-17	37	44	
	-1	8	17	22	-2	44	
	10	13	1	25	-5	44	
	55	19	-44	10	4	44	
	-35	1	64	4	10	44	
	44	44	44	44	44	44	

3	mgc				24
	15	3	6	24	
	-1	8	17	24	
	10	13	1	24	
	24	24	24	24	

Example 2.10. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.5:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154	
		-120	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	-707	154
		-96	138	91	220	-28	-31	-34	-37	-156	-37	124	154
		-99	-11	-102	-184	64	67	70	73	73	76	127	154
		-102	280	-244	13	7	10	-11	35	-112	148	130	154
		-105	-43	79	7	10	13	22	2	46	-10	133	154
		-108	-46	82	10	13	7	25	-1	49	-13	136	154
		-111	-49	85	53	19	-36	12	6	52	-16	139	154
		-114	-52	88	-29	5	60	6	12	55	-19	142	154
		-117	-84	43	-52	31	34	37	40	58	19	145	154
		391	-7	4	88	5	2	-1	-4	61	-22	-363	154
		735	-69	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-90	-93	148	154
		154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

The above Example 2.10 is obtained by applying the condition $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										126
		138	91	220	-28	-31	-34	-37	-156	-37		126
		-11	-102	-184	64	67	70	73	73	76		126
		280	-244	13	7	10	-11	35	-112	148		126
		-43	79	7	10	13	22	2	46	-10		126
		-46	82	10	13	7	25	-1	49	-13		126
		-49	85	53	19	-36	12	6	52	-16		126
		-52	88	-29	5	60	6	12	55	-19		126
		-84	43	-52	31	34	37	40	58	19		126
		-7	4	88	5	2	-1	-4	61	-22		126
		126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126		126

5	mgc						54
		13	7	10	-11	35	54
		7	10	13	22	2	54
		10	13	7	25	-1	54
		53	19	-36	12	6	54
		-29	5	60	6	12	54
		54	54	54	54	54	54

3	mgc				30
		13	7	10	30
		7	10	13	30
		10	13	7	30
		30	30	30	30

Result 2.6. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

R-L-A50	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	L+A50-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41
R-L-A42	$(S-L)/2+A31+2*A15+A20-A21$	A31	$3*(S-L)/4+A22+A23+A24+A25$	$(L-S)/2-A22$	$(L-S)/2-A23$	$(L-S)/2-A24$	$(L-S)/2-A25$	$(5*S-L)/4-A31-A15-A20$	$(L-S)/2-A31-A15+A21$	A42
R-L-A43	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A20-A26+A15$	L-S-A31-2*A15-A20+A21	$5*(L-S)/4-A22-A23-A24-A25$	A22	A23	A24	A25	A31+A15-A21	A26	A43
R-L-A44	$3*(S-L)/4+A27+A28+A29+A30$	$5*(L-S)/4-A27-A28-A29-A30$	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	$5*(L-S)/4-A16-A17-A18-A19$	$3*(S-L)/4+A16+A17+A18+A19$	A44
R-L-A45	$(L-S)/2-A27$	A27	$3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4$	A1+A2-M/3	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6$	A16	$(L-S)/2-A16$	A45
R-L-A46	$(L-S)/2-A28$	A28	A5	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	S-M-A5	A17	$(L-S)/2-A17$	A46
R-L-A47	$(L-S)/2-A29$	A29	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A18	$(L-S)/2-A18$	A47
R-L-A48	$(L-S)/2-A30$	A30	$4*M-2*S-A9$	$A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7$	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	A19	$(L-S)/2-A19$	A48
R-L-A49	L-S-A31-2*A15+A21-2*A20+A26	A15	$5*(L-S)/4-A11-A12-A13-A14$	A11	A12	A13	A14	A20	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A31+A15-A21+A20-A26$	A49
$2*A50-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49$	$(L-S)/2-A15$	$(9*S-5*L)/4+A15+A20-A21$	$3*(S-L)/4+A11+A12+A13+A14$	$(L-S)/2-A11$	$(L-S)/2-A12$	$(L-S)/2-A13$	$(L-S)/2-A14$	A21	$(L-S)/2-A20$	R-L-2*A50+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49
A35+A34-A50+A33+A39+A38+A37+A36+A41+9*L+A40-8*R	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	A50

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **double-digit bordered** magic squares of order 9 having again a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5, where magic square of order 3 is in the middle. It contains magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal width and length. The letters M, S, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the conditions given in (1) and (4), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $S := \frac{5}{3} \times M$. To avoid decimal entries the difference between S and L should be multiple of 4. Moreover, the magic square of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.11. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.6:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-168
1	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-231	184	
9	55	40	82	1	0	-1	-2	-49	-2	51	184	
8	-2	-23	-50	31	32	33	34	34	35	52	184	
7	102	-70	15	-10	20	17	18	-26	58	53	184	
6	-4	36	60	13	5	6	-24	25	7	54	184	
5	-5	37	14	1	8	15	22	26	6	55	184	
4	-6	38	13	10	11	3	23	27	5	56	184	
3	-7	39	-42	46	16	19	21	28	4	57	184	
2	-17	24	-6	20	21	22	23	29	8	58	184	
140	8	3	38	12	11	10	9	30	3	-80	184	
-1	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	59	184	
184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	184	

The magic square given in Example 2.11 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								120
136	91	217	-26	-29	-32	-35	-167	-35	120	
-26	-98	-179	64	67	70	73	73	76	120	
277	-239	15	3	6	-17	37	-107	145	120	
-41	79	-1	8	17	22	-2	46	-8	120	
-44	82	10	13	1	25	-5	49	-11	120	
-47	85	55	19	-44	10	4	52	-14	120	
-50	88	-35	1	64	4	10	55	-17	120	
-80	43	-47	31	34	37	40	58	4	120	
-5	-11	85	7	4	1	-2	61	-20	120	
120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	

5	mgc					44
15	3	6	-17	37	44	
-1	8	17	22	-2	44	
10	13	1	25	-5	44	
55	19	-44	10	4	44	
-35	1	64	4	10	44	
44	44	44	44	44	44	

3	mgc			24
15	3	6	24	
-1	8	17	24	
10	13	1	24	
24	24	24	24	

Example 2.12. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.6:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
	-27	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-211	176
	-19	55	40	82	1	0	-1	-2	-29	-2	51	176
	-20	18	-23	-50	31	32	33	34	34	35	52	176
	-21	102	-70	15	14	16	17	18	-26	58	53	176
	-22	-4	36	24	5	21	22	8	25	7	54	176
	-23	-5	37	14	33	16	-1	18	26	6	55	176
	-24	-6	38	13	10	11	27	19	27	5	56	176
	-25	-7	39	14	18	16	15	17	28	4	57	176
	-26	-17	24	-6	20	21	22	23	29	28	58	176
	140	8	23	38	12	11	10	9	30	3	-108	176
	243	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	59	176
	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176

The above Example 2.12 is obtained by applying the conditions $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $S := \frac{5}{3} \times M$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										144
	55	40	82	1	0	-1	-2	-29	-2			144
	18	-23	-50	31	32	33	34	34	35			144
	102	-70	15	14	16	17	18	-26	58			144
	-4	36	24	5	21	22	8	25	7			144
	-5	37	14	33	16	-1	18	26	6			144
	-6	38	13	10	11	27	19	27	5			144
	-7	39	14	18	16	15	17	28	4			144
	-17	24	-6	20	21	22	23	29	28			144
	8	23	38	12	11	10	9	30	3			144
	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144

5	mgc						80
	15	14	16	17	18	80	
	24	5	21	22	8	80	
	14	33	16	-1	18	80	
	13	10	11	27	19	80	
	14	18	16	15	17	80	
	80	80	80	80	80	80	

3	mgc				48
	5	21	22	48	
	33	16	-1	48	
	10	11	27	48	
	48	48	48	48	

Result 2.7. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

R-L-A47	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	L+A47-A30-A31- A32-A33-A34-A35- A36-A37-A38
R-L-A39	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$	A23	L-T-A23	A39
R-L-A40	A13	A12	$3*(T-S)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A24	L-T-A24	A40
R-L-A41	$A15+A16-(T-S)/4$	$3*(T-S)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-S/3$	$2*S/3-A2$	$2*S/3-A1$	$3*(T-S)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-S)/4$	A25	L-T-A25	A41
R-L-A42	$(T-S)/2-A15$	A15	$4*S/3-2*A1-A2$	S/3	$2*A1+A2-2*S/3$	A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A26	L-T-A26	A42
R-L-A43	$(T-S)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	S-A1-A2	A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	$7*(L-T)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	$5*(T-L)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28$	A43
R-L-A44	$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-S)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*S-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A27	L-T-A27	A44
R-L-A45	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A4$	$(T-S)/2-A5$	$A14+A13-A6$	$T-3*S-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$	A28	L-T-A28	A45
R-L-A46	A18	$(5*T-3*S)/2-L+A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*A7-A8-A24+A23$	A19	A20	$(9*L+3*S)/2-6*T-2*A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*A7+A8+A24-A23-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A21	A22	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$	A46
$2*A47-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46$	L-T-A18	$2*L+(3*S-7*T)/2-A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*A7+A8+A24-A23$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$5*T-(7*L+3*S)/2+2*A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*A7-A8-A24+A23+A19+A20+A21+A22$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2	$R-L-2*A47+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46$
$9*L-8*R+A32+A31+A30-A47+A36+A35+A34+A33+A38+A37$	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	A47

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 9 having a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at the upper-left corner. It contains magic square of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×7 are of equal width and length. The letters M, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. To avoid decimal entries the difference between T and S should be multiple of 4. Moreover, the magic square of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.13. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.7:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										134	
		-120	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	-719	151
		-96	-20	50	67	-14	-17	35	-29	77	-27	125	151
		-99	47	44	-43	38	41	53	-108	80	-30	128	151
		-102	97	-73	17	2	5	-25	49	83	-33	131	151
		-105	-29	53	-4	8	20	29	-5	86	-36	134	151
		-108	-32	56	11	14	-1	32	-8	-332	382	137	151
		-111	59	74	-7	20	23	-123	26	89	-39	140	151
		-114	-50	-132	31	4	1	71	147	92	-42	143	151
		-117	62	-47	65	68	-118	71	74	25	-78	146	151
		392	-12	97	-15	-18	168	-21	-24	-78	25	-363	151
		731	-69	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-90	-93	149	151
		151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151

The magic square given in Example 2.13 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										122
		-20	50	67	-14	-17	35	-29	77	-27	122	
		47	44	-43	38	41	53	-108	80	-30	122	
		97	-73	17	2	5	-25	49	83	-33	122	
		-29	53	-4	8	20	29	-5	86	-36	122	
		-32	56	11	14	-1	32	-8	-332	382	122	
		59	74	-7	20	23	-123	26	89	-39	122	
		-50	-132	31	4	1	71	147	92	-42	122	
		62	-47	65	68	-118	71	74	25	-78	122	
		-12	97	-15	-18	168	-21	-24	-78	25	122	
		122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							72
		-20	50	67	-14	-17	35	-29	72
		47	44	-43	38	41	53	-108	72
		97	-73	17	2	5	-25	49	72
		-29	53	-4	8	20	29	-5	72
		-32	56	11	14	-1	32	-8	72
		59	74	-7	20	23	-123	26	72
		-50	-132	31	4	1	71	147	72
		72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72

3	mgc				24
		17	2	5	24
		-4	8	20	24
		11	14	-1	24
		24	24	24	24

Example 2.14. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.7:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
	-117	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	-697	176
	-93	-26	50	70	-20	-23	35	-14	77	-5	125	176
	-96	47	44	-52	38	41	32	-78	80	-8	128	176
	-99	100	-82	13	10	13	-34	52	83	-11	131	176
	-102	-35	53	12	12	12	29	-11	86	-14	134	176
	-105	-38	56	11	14	11	32	-14	-255	327	137	176
	-108	59	53	-16	20	23	-93	26	89	-17	140	176
	-111	-35	-102	34	-2	-5	71	111	92	-20	143	176
	-114	62	-87	65	68	-1	71	74	36	-144	146	176
	392	10	159	7	4	73	1	-2	-144	36	-360	176
	729	-66	-69	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-90	149	176
	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176

The above Example 2.14 is obtained by applying the condition $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									144
	-26	50	70	-20	-23	35	-14	77	-5	144	
	47	44	-52	38	41	32	-78	80	-8	144	
	100	-82	13	10	13	-34	52	83	-11	144	
	-35	53	12	12	12	29	-11	86	-14	144	
	-38	56	11	14	11	32	-14	-255	327	144	
	59	53	-16	20	23	-93	26	89	-17	144	
	-35	-102	34	-2	-5	71	111	92	-20	144	
	62	-87	65	68	-1	71	74	36	-144	144	
	10	159	7	4	73	1	-2	-144	36	144	
	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							72
	-26	50	70	-20	-23	35	-14	72	
	47	44	-52	38	41	32	-78	72	
	100	-82	13	10	13	-34	52	72	
	-35	53	12	12	12	29	-11	72	
	-38	56	11	14	11	32	-14	72	
	59	53	-16	20	23	-93	26	72	
	-35	-102	34	-2	-5	71	111	72	
	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	

3	mgc				36
	13	10	13	36	
	12	12	12	36	
	11	14	11	36	
	36	36	36	36	

Result 2.8. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

R-L-A46	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	L+A46-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37
R-L-A38	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	$2*L-5*T-A23-A7+2*S+2*A14+2*A10+2*A11+A16$	$4*T-L+A23+A7-2*S-2*A14-2*A10-2*A11-A16$	A38
R-L-A39	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	L-T-A23	A23	A39
R-L-A40	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	$5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13$	$3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A1$	L-T-A24	A24	A40
R-L-A41	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15	L-T-A25	A25	A41
R-L-A42	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16	$(13*T-7*L)/2+A25+A24+2*A23+A27+A26+A7-2*S-2*A14-2*A10-2*A11-A16$	$(9*L-15*T)/2-A25-A24-2*A23-A27-A26-A7+2*S+2*A14+2*A10+2*A11+A16$	A42
R-L-A43	T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13	A10	$A7+A8+3*(T-S)/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13$	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	L-T-A26	A26	A43
R-L-A44	A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	$(S-T)/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13$	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	L-T-A27	A27	A44
R-L-A45	A18	A18-2*A15-A12	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A20-A19-A22+2*A15+A12-2*A18$	A19	A20	A21	A22	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$	A45
$2*A46-A29-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45$	L-T-A18	L-T+2*A15+A12-A18	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A20+A19+A22-2*A15-A12+2*A18$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2	R-L-2*A46+A29+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45
$9*L-8*R+A35+A36+A37+A31+A32+A33+A34-A46+A29+A30$	R-L-A29	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	A46

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 9 and 7 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. To avoid decimal entries the difference between T and L, and L and R should be multiple of 2. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.15. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.8:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										24	
		-24	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	-291	162
		-16	21	22	-52	23	24	33	1	112	-64	58	162
		-17	33	25	12	26	-58	34	0	5	43	59	162
		-18	17	-54	27	35	13	-53	87	4	44	60	162
		-19	29	23	18	-63	31	35	-1	3	45	61	162
		-20	-62	22	33	17	28	36	-2	41	7	62	162
		-21	10	30	-18	31	32	17	-30	2	46	63	162
		-22	24	4	52	3	2	-30	17	1	47	64	162
		-23	38	-64	32	39	40	41	42	24	-72	65	162
		147	10	112	16	9	8	7	6	-72	24	-105	162
		195	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	66	162
		162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162

The magic square given in Example 2.15 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									120
		21	22	-52	23	24	33	1	112	-64	120
		33	25	12	26	-58	34	0	5	43	120
		17	-54	27	35	13	-53	87	4	44	120
		29	23	18	-63	31	35	-1	3	45	120
		-62	22	33	17	28	36	-2	41	7	120
		10	30	-18	31	32	17	-30	2	46	120
		24	4	52	3	2	-30	17	1	47	120
		38	-64	32	39	40	41	42	24	-72	120
		10	112	16	9	8	7	6	-72	24	120
		120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							72
		21	22	-52	23	24	33	1	72
		33	25	12	26	-58	34	0	72
		17	-54	27	35	13	-53	87	72
		29	23	18	-63	31	35	-1	72
		-62	22	33	17	28	36	-2	72
		10	30	-18	31	32	17	-30	72
		24	4	52	3	2	-30	17	72
		72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72

5	pan	38	38	38	38	38		
		38	21	22	-52	23	24	38
		38	33	25	12	26	-58	38
		38	17	-54	27	35	13	38
		38	29	23	18	-63	31	38
			-62	22	33	17	28	38
		38	38	38	38	38	38	38

Example 2.16. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.8:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										220
	-26	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	-231	220
	-18	21	22	-52	23	24	33	19	142	-52	58	220
	-19	33	25	12	26	-58	34	18	47	43	59	220
	-20	17	-54	27	35	13	-8	60	46	44	60	220
	-21	29	23	18	-63	31	35	17	45	45	61	220
	-22	-62	22	33	17	28	36	16	-52	142	62	220
	-23	28	30	9	31	32	26	-66	44	46	63	220
	-24	24	22	43	21	20	-66	26	43	47	64	220
	-25	38	-64	179	39	40	41	42	45	-180	65	220
	147	52	154	-89	51	50	49	48	-180	45	-107	220
	271	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	66	220
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

The above Example 2.16 is obtained by applying the condition $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									180
	21	22	-52	23	24	33	19	142	-52	180	
	33	25	12	26	-58	34	18	47	43	180	
	17	-54	27	35	13	-8	60	46	44	180	
	29	23	18	-63	31	35	17	45	45	180	
	-62	22	33	17	28	36	16	-52	142	180	
	28	30	9	31	32	26	-66	44	46	180	
	24	22	43	21	20	-66	26	43	47	180	
	38	-64	179	39	40	41	42	45	-180	180	
	52	154	-89	51	50	49	48	-180	45	180	
	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							90
	21	22	-52	23	24	33	19	90	
	33	25	12	26	-58	34	18	90	
	17	-54	27	35	13	-8	60	90	
	29	23	18	-63	31	35	17	90	
	-62	22	33	17	28	36	16	90	
	28	30	9	31	32	26	-66	90	
	24	22	43	21	20	-66	26	90	
	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	90	

5	pan	38	38	38	38	38
38	21	22	-52	23	24	38
38	33	25	12	26	-58	38
38	17	-54	27	35	13	38
38	29	23	18	-63	31	38
	-62	22	33	17	28	38
	38	38	38	38	38	38

Result 2.9. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

R-L-A45	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	L+A45-A28-A29- A30-A31-A32-A33- A34-A35-A36
R-L-A37	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6	A5+A6-(S-M)/2	A11	T-S-A11	A21	L-T-A21	A37
R-L-A38	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12	A22	L-T-A22	A38
R-L-A39	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13	A23	L-T-A23	A39
R-L-A40	A4-A1-A2+2*A5+ A6-(S-M)/2	A4	A1+2*(S-M)- 2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6	(S-M)/2	2*M-S	5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12- A13-A14	3*(S-T)/2+ A11+A12+A13+A14	A24	L-T-A24	A40
R-L-A41	A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2- 2*A5-A6-A4	S-M-A4	2*A4-S+M-A1- A2+2*A5+A6	2*M-S	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14	7*(L-T)/2-A21-A22- A23-A24-A25-A26	5*(T-L)/2+A21 +A22+A23+A24+ A25+A26	A41
R-L-A42	T-3*S/2- M/2+A8+2*A4-A1- A2+2*A5+A12-A11	A8	A9	3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8- 2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5- A12+A11-A9-A10	A10	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A25	L-T-A25	A42
R-L-A43	S/2+M/2-A8- 2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5- A12+A11	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	2*A8+2*A4-A1- A2+2*A5+A12-A11 +A9+A10-T/2-M/2	T-S-A10	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A26	L-T-A26	A43
R-L-A44	A16	5*S-4*T-L+A16 +2*A13+2*A4+2*A 12+A21-A22-A1- A2+2*A9+2*A8+2 *A5+A10+A14	A17	A18	(9*L+T)/2-5*S-2*A16- 2*A13-2*A4-2*A12- A21+A22+A1+A2-2*A9- 2*A8-2*A5-A10-A14- A17-A18-A19-A20	A19	A20	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L	A44
2*A45-A28-A29- A30-A31-A32-A33- A34-A35- A36+A37+A38 +A39+A40+A41+ A42+A43+A44	L-T-A16	2*L+3*T-5*S-A16- 2*A13-2*A4-2*A12- A21+A22+A1+A2- 2*A9-2*A8-2*A5- A10-A14	L-T-A17	L-T-A18	5*S-(3*T+7*L)/2 +2*A16+2*A13+2*A4+ 2*A12+A21-A22-A1- A2+2*A9+2*A8 +2*A5+A10+A14+A17 +A18+A19+A20	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2	R-L-2*A45 +A28+A29+A30+ A31+A32+A33+A3 4+A35+A36-A37- A38-A39-A40-A41- A42-A43-A44
9*L-8*R+A30 +A29+A28-A45 +A34+A33+A32+ A31+A36+A35	R-L-A28	R-L-A29	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	A45

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 9, 7 and 5 having a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. To avoid decimal entries the pairs (M, S), (S, T) and (T, L) should be multiple of 2. Moreover, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.17. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.9:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-116
	-3	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	-223	152
	5	15	4	5	-1	21	21	3	31	1	47	152
	4	-2	8	18	15	5	22	2	32	0	48	152
	3	11	12	1	16	4	23	1	33	-1	49	152
	2	27	14	-11	10	4	-30	54	34	-2	50	152
	1	-7	6	31	4	10	24	0	-89	121	51	152
	0	44	18	19	-41	20	12	-4	35	-3	52	152
	-1	-20	6	5	65	4	-4	12	36	-4	53	152
	-2	26	116	27	28	-144	29	30	16	-28	54	152
	136	6	-84	5	4	176	3	2	-28	16	-84	152
	7	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	55	152
	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152

The magic square given in Example 2.17 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									100
	15	4	5	-1	21	21	3	31	1	100	
	-2	8	18	15	5	22	2	32	0	100	
	11	12	1	16	4	23	1	33	-1	100	
	27	14	-11	10	4	-30	54	34	-2	100	
	-7	6	31	4	10	24	0	-89	121	100	
	44	18	19	-41	20	12	-4	35	-3	100	
	-20	6	5	65	4	-4	12	36	-4	100	
	26	116	27	28	-144	29	30	16	-28	100	
	6	-84	5	4	176	3	2	-28	16	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							68
	15	4	5	-1	21	21	3	68	
	-2	8	18	15	5	22	2	68	
	11	12	1	16	4	23	1	68	
	27	14	-11	10	4	-30	54	68	
	-7	6	31	4	10	24	0	68	
	44	18	19	-41	20	12	-4	68	
	-20	6	5	65	4	-4	12	68	
	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	

5	mgc						44
	15	4	5	-1	21	44	
	-2	8	18	15	5	44	
	11	12	1	16	4	44	
	27	14	-11	10	4	44	
	-7	6	31	4	10	44	
	44	44	44	44	44	44	

3	mgc				24
	15	4	5	24	
	-2	8	18	24	
	11	12	1	24	
	24	24	24	24	

Example 2.18. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.9:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										121
	-33	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	-224	121
	-25	16	2	3	5	19	21	3	31	-1	47	121
	-26	-6	7	20	15	9	22	2	32	-2	48	121
	-27	11	12	-2	16	8	23	1	33	-3	49	121
	-28	25	14	-3	12	-3	-30	54	34	-4	50	121
	-29	-1	10	27	-3	12	24	0	-96	126	51	121
	-30	45	18	19	-42	20	12	-3	35	-5	52	121
	-31	-21	6	5	66	4	-3	12	36	-6	53	121
	-32	26	118	27	28	-153	29	30	15	-21	54	121
	136	4	-88	3	2	183	1	0	-21	15	-114	121
	246	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	55	121
	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121

The above Example 2.18 is obtained by applying the condition $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									99
	16	2	3	5	19	21	3	31	-1	99	
	-6	7	20	15	9	22	2	32	-2	99	
	11	12	-2	16	8	23	1	33	-3	99	
	25	14	-3	12	-3	-30	54	34	-4	99	
	-1	10	27	-3	12	24	0	-96	126	99	
	45	18	19	-42	20	12	-3	35	-5	99	
	-21	6	5	66	4	-3	12	36	-6	99	
	26	118	27	28	-153	29	30	15	-21	99	
	4	-88	3	2	183	1	0	-21	15	99	
	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	99	

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							69
	16	2	3	5	19	21	3	69	
	-6	7	20	15	9	22	2	69	
	11	12	-2	16	8	23	1	69	
	25	14	-3	12	-3	-30	54	69	
	-1	10	27	-3	12	24	0	69	
	45	18	19	-42	20	12	-3	69	
	-21	6	5	66	4	-3	12	69	
	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	69	

5	mgc						45
	16	2	3	5	19	45	
	-6	7	20	15	9	45	
	11	12	-2	16	8	45	
	25	14	-3	12	-3	45	
	-1	10	27	-3	12	45	
	45	45	45	45	45	45	

3	mgc				21
	16	2	3	21	
	-6	7	20	21	
	11	12	-2	21	
	21	21	21	21	

Result 2.10. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A47	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	L+A47-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38
R-L-A39	A6	2*M-A9-S+A7	S-M-A7	S-M-A6	A9	A14	T-S-A14	2*L-5*T-A24-A7+2*S+2*A15+2*A11+2*A12+A17	4*T-L+A24+A7-2*S-2*A15-2*A11-2*A12-A17	A39
R-L-A40	2*S-3*M+A9-2*A7+A2+A1-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	2*M-S+A4+2*A7-A2-A1-A9	A15	T-S-A15	L-T-A24	A24	A40
R-L-A41	2*A7+S-M-A6-A2-A1	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	A6-2*A7+A2+A1	(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A17-A16-A15-A14	(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A14+A15+A16+A17	L-T-A25	A25	A41
R-L-A42	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16	L-T-A26	A26	A42
R-L-A43	4*M-2*S-A9	A9+2*S-3*M-A7	A7	A6	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17	(13*T-7*L)/2+A26+A25+2*A24+A28+A27+A7-2*S-2*A15-2*A11-2*A12-A17	(9*L-15*T)/2-A26-A25-2*A24-A28-A27-A7+2*S+2*A15+2*A11+2*A12+A17	A43
R-L-A44	T-2*S-A7+A11+M+A6+A15-A14	A11	A7-(1/2)*S-M-A6+(3/2)*T-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	L-T-A27	A27	A44
R-L-A45	A7-A11+S-M-A6-A15+A14	T-S-A11	A13+A12+2*A11-A7+M+A6+A15-A14-(1/2)*T-(1/2)*S	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	L-T-A28	A28	A45
R-L-A46	A19	A19-2*A16-A13	(7/2)*L-(7/2)*T-A22-A21-A20-A23+2*A16+A13-2*A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L	A46
2*A47-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46	L-T-A19	L-T+2*A16+A13-A19	(5/2)*T-(5/2)*L+A22+A21+A20+A23-2*A16-A13+2*A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2	R-L-2*A47+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46
9*L-8*R+A32+A31+A30-A47+A36+A35+A34+A33+A38+A37	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	A47

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 9 and 7 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner. It contains a magic square of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of orders 2×5 and 2×7 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. To avoid decimal entries the pairs (M, S), (S, T) and (T, L) should be multiple of 2. Moreover, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.19. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.10:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										280	
		-17	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	-139	240
		-9	16	58	13	14	19	24	6	2	48	49	240
		-10	-36	-7	48	49	66	25	5	16	34	50	240
		-11	25	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	15	35	51	240
		-12	14	11	12	67	16	26	4	14	36	52	240
		-13	101	-28	17	16	14	27	3	103	-53	53	240
		-14	21	21	-12	22	23	15	60	13	37	54	240
		-15	9	9	42	8	7	60	15	12	38	55	240
		-16	29	-46	66	30	31	32	33	25	0	56	240
		138	21	96	-16	20	19	18	17	0	25	-98	240
		219	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	57	240
		240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

The magic square given in Example 2.19 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									200
		16	58	13	14	19	24	6	2	48	200
		-36	-7	48	49	66	25	5	16	34	200
		25	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	15	35	200
		14	11	12	67	16	26	4	14	36	200
		101	-28	17	16	14	27	3	103	-53	200
		21	21	-12	22	23	15	60	13	37	200
		9	9	42	8	7	60	15	12	38	200
		29	-46	66	30	31	32	33	25	0	200
		21	96	-16	20	19	18	17	0	25	200
		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							150
		16	58	13	14	19	24	6	150
		-36	-7	48	49	66	25	5	150
		25	86	30	-26	5	-27	57	150
		14	11	12	67	16	26	4	150
		101	-28	17	16	14	27	3	150
		21	21	-12	22	23	15	60	150
		9	9	42	8	7	60	15	150
		150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

5	semi						210
		16	58	13	14	19	120
		-36	-7	48	49	66	120
		25	86	30	-26	5	120
		14	11	12	67	16	120
		101	-28	17	16	14	120
		120	120	120	120	120	120

3	mgc				90
		-7	48	49	90
		86	30	-26	90
		11	12	67	90
		90	90	90	90

Example 2.20. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.10:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										132
	-33	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	-231	132
	-25	16	14	15	16	19	24	46	-262	220	49	132
	-26	10	7	20	21	22	25	45	-76	34	50	132
	-27	27	30	16	2	5	73	-3	-77	35	51	132
	-28	14	11	12	25	18	26	44	-78	36	52	132
	-29	13	18	17	16	16	27	43	505	-547	53	132
	-30	59	21	50	22	23	35	-60	-79	37	54	132
	-31	11	49	20	48	47	-60	35	-80	38	55	132
	-32	29	-46	-256	30	31	32	33	-21	276	56	132
	138	-71	4	214	-72	-73	-74	-75	276	-21	-114	132
	255	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	57	132
	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132

The above Example 2.20 is obtained by applying the condition $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. Even though it is not necessary, but an extra condition $S := \frac{5}{3} \times M$ is applied to bring a **semi-magic** square of order 5 as magic square. See below the magic squares appearing in second example of Example 2.19.

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									108
	16	14	15	16	19	24	46	-262	220	108	
	10	7	20	21	22	25	45	-76	34	108	
	27	30	16	2	5	73	-3	-77	35	108	
	14	11	12	25	18	26	44	-78	36	108	
	13	18	17	16	16	27	43	505	-547	108	
	59	21	50	22	23	35	-60	-79	37	108	
	11	49	20	48	47	-60	35	-80	38	108	
	29	-46	-256	30	31	32	33	-21	276	108	
	-71	4	214	-72	-73	-74	-75	276	-21	108	
	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	108	

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							150
	16	14	15	16	19	24	46	150	
	10	7	20	21	22	25	45	150	
	27	30	16	2	5	73	-3	150	
	14	11	12	25	18	26	44	150	
	13	18	17	16	16	27	43	150	
	59	21	50	22	23	35	-60	150	
	11	49	20	48	47	-60	35	150	
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	

5	mgc						80
	16	14	15	16	19	80	
	10	7	20	21	22	80	
	27	30	16	2	5	80	
	14	11	12	25	18	80	
	13	18	17	16	16	80	
	80	80	80	80	80	80	

3	mgc				48
	7	20	21	48	
	30	16	2	48	
	11	12	25	48	
	48	48	48	48	

Result 2.11. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A65	A48	A49	A50	A51	A52	A53	A54	A55	A56	L+A65-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56
R-L-A57	T+A16+A30+A12-A24+A26-A20-A19-A23+A8-A22-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8+A22+A21-A16-A30-A12	A41	L-T-A41	A57
R-L-A58	A6	A7	A19+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24-A27-A31-A2-A10-A15	A24+A28+A27+A25+A20+A19+A29+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A2+A1-A34-3*A16-A32-A30-A12-A11-A10	T+A34+3*A16+A15+A32+A31+A30+A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A28-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A9-A6-A22-A5-A4-A1-A21	A8	A9	A42	L-T-A42	A58
R-L-A59	A24-A26-A25+A20+A23-A8-A6+A22+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A16-A14-2*A30-A12	A18-A16+A14+A33+A30-A13-A12-A11-2*A10+A25+A19+A23+A8-A7+A6-A22+A5-A34	A10	A11	A12	T+A34-A18+2*A16-A33+A30+A12+A10-A24+A26-A20-A19-2*A23+A7-2*A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21	A13	A43	L-T-A43	A59
R-L-A60	A14	A34-A18-A17-2*A16-A15-A14-A30+A13-A12+2*A24-A26+A20+A19+A29+A23+A9-A8+A22+A21	A15	A16	A17	A18	T-A34+A16+A30-A13+A12-2*A24+A26-A20-A19-A29-A23-A9+A8-A22-A21	A44	L-T-A44	A60
R-L-A61	A19	A20	T-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24	A21	A22	A23	A24	A45	L-T-A45	A61
R-L-A62	A25	A26	A27	T+A34+2*A16+A30+A12+A10-A24-A28-A27-A25-A20-A19-A29-A23+A8+A7-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21	A28	A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A34-2*A16-A30-A12-A10	A29	A46	L-T-A46	A62
R-L-A63	A30	T+A17+3*A16+A15-A33-A9+2*A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A6-A5-A1-A21	A31	A32	2*A24+A25+2*A20+2*A19+A29+2*A23+A9+A6+A5+A1+A21-A34-A17-3*A16-A15-A32-A31-A30-2*A12-A11-2*A10	A33	A34	7*(L-T)/2-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46	5*(T-L)/2+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46	A63
R-L-A64	A36-A1-A21+A31-A5-A4-A3-A2-A29-A23+A8+A7-A25-A20-A19+A10-A24-A28-A27+2*A16+A30+A12+A22+A34+A13+A18-A41+A42+L-T	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A1+A21-A31+A5+A4+A3+A2+A29+A23-A8-A7+A25+A20+A19-A10+A24+A28+A27-2*A16-A30-A12-A22-A34-A13-A18+A41-A42+(5/2)*L-(5/2)*T-A40-A39-A38-A37-2*A36	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L	A64
2*A65-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56+A57+A58+A59+A60+A61+A62+A63+A64	A1+A21-A31+A5+A4+A3+A2+A29+A23-A8-A7+A25+A20+A19-A10+A24+A28+A27-2*A16-A30-A12-A22-A34-A13-A18+A41-A42-A36	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	(3/2)*T+A40+A39+A38+A37+2*A36-A1-A21+A31-A5-A4-A3-A2-A29-A23+A8+A7-A25-A20-A19+A10-A24-A28-A27+2*A16+A30+A12+A22+A34+A13+A18-A41+A42-(3/2)*L	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2	R-L-2*A65+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56-A57-A58-A59-A60-A61-A62-A63-A64
9*L-8*R+A56+A55+A54+A53+A52+A51+A50+A49+A48-A65	R-L-A48	R-L-A49	R-L-A50	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	A65

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 9 having a magic square of order 7 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal width and length. The letters T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 7, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. To avoid decimal entries the pairs (T, L) should be multiple of 2. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.21. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.11:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										213
-45	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	-332	181	
-37	9	11	12	13	14	15	47	51	-21	67	181	
-38	16	17	54	25	-28	18	19	52	-22	68	181	
-39	-32	56	20	21	22	11	23	53	-23	69	181	
-40	24	76	25	26	27	28	-85	54	-24	70	181	
-41	29	30	-68	31	32	33	34	55	-25	71	181	
-42	35	36	37	-37	38	-27	39	56	-26	72	181	
-43	40	-105	41	42	16	43	44	-216	246	73	181	
-44	43	46	47	48	49	50	-178	15	31	74	181	
156	-13	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	208	31	15	-126	181	
394	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	-33	-34	-35	-36	75	181	
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	

The magic square given in Example 2.21 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									151
9	11	12	13	14	15	47	51	-21	151		
16	17	54	25	-28	18	19	52	-22	151		
-32	56	20	21	22	11	23	53	-23	151		
24	76	25	26	27	28	-85	54	-24	151		
29	30	-68	31	32	33	34	55	-25	151		
35	36	37	-37	38	-27	39	56	-26	151		
40	-105	41	42	16	43	44	-216	246	151		
43	46	47	48	49	50	-178	15	31	151		
-13	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	208	31	15	151		
151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151	151		

2	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							121
9	11	12	13	14	15	47	121		
16	17	54	25	-28	18	19	121		
-32	56	20	21	22	11	23	121		
24	76	25	26	27	28	-85	121		
29	30	-68	31	32	33	34	121		
35	36	37	-37	38	-27	39	121		
40	-105	41	42	16	43	44	121		
121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121		

Example 2.22. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.11:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										187
	-41	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	-330	187
	-33	9	11	12	13	14	15	47	51	-19	67	187
	-34	16	17	54	25	-28	18	19	52	-20	68	187
	-35	-32	56	20	21	22	11	23	53	-21	69	187
	-36	24	76	25	26	27	28	-85	54	-22	70	187
	-37	29	30	-68	31	32	33	34	55	-23	71	187
	-38	35	36	37	-37	38	-27	39	56	-24	72	187
	-39	40	-105	41	42	16	43	44	-209	241	73	187
	-40	45	46	47	48	49	50	-173	16	25	74	187
	156	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	205	25	16	-122	187
	364	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-30	-31	-32	75	187
	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187

The above Example 2.22 is obtained by applying the condition $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
	9	11	12	13	14	15	47	51	-19			153
	16	17	54	25	-28	18	19	52	-20			153
	-32	56	20	21	22	11	23	53	-21			153
	24	76	25	26	27	28	-85	54	-22			153
	29	30	-68	31	32	33	34	55	-23			153
	35	36	37	-37	38	-27	39	56	-24			153
	40	-105	41	42	16	43	44	-209	241			153
	45	46	47	48	49	50	-173	16	25			153
	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	205	25	16			153
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153			153

2	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT										121
	9	11	12	13	14	15	47					121
	16	17	54	25	-28	18	19					121
	-32	56	20	21	22	11	23					121
	24	76	25	26	27	28	-85					121
	29	30	-68	31	32	33	34					121
	35	36	37	-37	38	-27	39					121
	40	-105	41	42	16	43	44					121
	121	121	121	121	121	121	121					121

Result 2.12. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A49	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	L+A49-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40
R-L-A41	A17	T-S+A10+A14-A13	A10	S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	A18	L-T-A25	A25	A41
R-L-A42	A14	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	T-S-A14	L-T-A26	A26	A42
R-L-A43	5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	5*S-4*T+ A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17	5*(T-L)/2+A26+A25+A27+A28+A29+A30	7*(L-T)/2-A26-A25-A27-A28-A29-A30	A43
R-L-A44	A15	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	T-S-A15	L-T-A27	A27	A44
R-L-A45	A16	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	T-S-A16	L-T-A28	A28	A45
R-L-A46	A13	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	T-S-A13	L-T-A29	A29	A46
R-L-A47	6*S-A18-4*T	A13-A10-A14	T-S-A10	A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10+T-2*S+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17	L-T-A30	A30	A47
R-L-A48	A20	5*T-A25+A26-A13+A18+A8-5*S+A7-A14+A10+A20-A16-A15-A17-L	(9*L-17*T)/2-A23-A22-A21-A24+A25-A26+A13-A18-A8+5*S-A7+A14-A10-2*A20+A16+ A15+A17	A21	A22	A23	A24	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L	A48
2*A49-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48	L-T-A20	2*L-6*T+A25-A26+A13-A18-A8+5*S-A7+A14-A10-A20+A16+A15+A17	(15*T-7*L)/2+A23+A22+A21+A24-A25+A26-A13+A18+A8-5*S+A7-A14+A10+2*A20-A16-A15-A17	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2	R-L-2*A49+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48
9*L-8*R+A34+A33+A32-A49+A38+A37+A36+A35+A40+A39	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	A49

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 9 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at the upper-left corner embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 in the middle. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal width and length. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. To avoid decimal entries the pairs (T, L) should be multiple of 2. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.23. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.12:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										212	
		-28	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	-255	221
		-20	37	51	30	-99	31	32	38	15	45	61	221
		-21	34	21	22	10	23	24	-14	14	46	62	221
		-22	-137	33	25	12	26	4	157	135	-75	63	221
		-23	35	17	8	27	35	13	-15	13	47	64	221
		-24	36	29	23	18	-1	31	-16	12	48	65	221
		-25	33	0	22	33	17	28	-13	11	49	66	221
		-26	82	-31	-10	119	-11	-12	-17	10	50	67	221
		-27	40	-91	91	41	42	43	44	30	-60	68	221
		150	20	151	-31	19	18	17	16	-60	30	-109	221
		287	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	69	221
		221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221

The magic square given in Example 2.23 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180
		37	51	30	-99	31	32	38	15	45	180	
		34	21	22	10	23	24	-14	14	46	180	
		-137	33	25	12	26	4	157	135	-75	180	
		35	17	8	27	35	13	-15	13	47	180	
		36	29	23	18	-1	31	-16	12	48	180	
		33	0	22	33	17	28	-13	11	49	180	
		82	-31	-10	119	-11	-12	-17	10	50	180	
		40	-91	91	41	42	43	44	30	-60	180	
		20	151	-31	19	18	17	16	-60	30	180	
		180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

7	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							220
		37	51	30	-99	31	32	38	120
		34	21	22	10	23	24	-14	120
		-137	33	25	12	26	4	157	120
		35	17	8	27	35	13	-15	120
		36	29	23	18	-1	31	-16	120
		33	0	22	33	17	28	-13	120
		82	-31	-10	119	-11	-12	-17	120
		120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

5	pan	100	100	100	100	100	100	
		100	21	22	10	23	24	100
		100	33	25	12	26	4	100
		100	17	8	27	35	13	100
		100	29	23	18	-1	31	100
			0	22	33	17	28	100
			100	100	100	100	100	100

Example 2.24. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.12:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										231
	-27	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	-246	231
	-19	37	69	30	-104	31	32	38	11	45	61	231
	-20	34	21	22	5	23	24	4	10	46	62	231
	-21	-42	33	25	12	26	-1	80	145	-89	63	231
	-22	35	17	3	27	35	13	3	9	47	64	231
	-23	36	29	23	18	-6	31	2	8	48	65	231
	-24	33	-5	22	33	17	28	5	7	49	66	231
	-25	0	-31	8	142	7	6	1	6	50	67	231
	-26	40	-10	-4	41	42	43	44	28	-35	68	231
	150	16	66	60	15	14	13	12	-35	28	-108	231
	288	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	69	231
	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231

The above Example 2.24 is obtained by applying the condition $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. An extra condition $R := \frac{7}{5} \times L$ is applied to bring a **semi-magic** square of order 7 to a magic square. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									189
	37	69	30	-104	31	32	38	11	45	189	
	34	21	22	5	23	24	4	10	46	189	
	-42	33	25	12	26	-1	80	145	-89	189	
	35	17	3	27	35	13	3	9	47	189	
	36	29	23	18	-6	31	2	8	48	189	
	33	-5	22	33	17	28	5	7	49	189	
	0	-31	8	142	7	6	1	6	50	189	
	40	-10	-4	41	42	43	44	28	-35	189	
	16	66	60	15	14	13	12	-35	28	189	
	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							133
	37	69	30	-104	31	32	38	133	
	34	21	22	5	23	24	4	133	
	-42	33	25	12	26	-1	80	133	
	35	17	3	27	35	13	3	133	
	36	29	23	18	-6	31	2	133	
	33	-5	22	33	17	28	5	133	
	0	-31	8	142	7	6	1	133	
	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	

5	pan	95	95	95	95	95
95	21	22	5	23	24	95
95	33	25	12	26	-1	95
95	17	3	27	35	13	95
95	29	23	18	-6	31	95
	-5	22	33	17	28	95
	95	95	95	95	95	95

Result 2.13. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A47	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	L+A47-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38
R-L-A39	A15	$(7/2)*T-(9/2)*S-A8+A5-2*M-A11$	A8	$(9/2)*S-A15-A16-A10-A9-A5+2*M-(5/2)*T+A11$	A9	A10	A16	A23	L-T-A23	A39
R-L-A40	$(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A15+A16-A14+2*A8-A5+2*M-A13-A11$	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	$(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A11-2*A8+A5-2*M+A13+A14-A16+A15$	A24	L-T-A24	A40
R-L-A41	$A5-(7/2)*S-2*M+(5/2)*T-2*A8$	$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	$(5/2)*S-(3/2)*T+2*A8-A5+2*M$	A25	L-T-A25	A41
R-L-A42	A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	T-S-A13	A26	L-T-A26	A42
R-L-A43	A14	$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	2*M-S	T-S-A14	$7*(L-T)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	$5*(T-L)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28$	A43
R-L-A44	A11	$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	2*M-S	(S-M)/2	T-S-A11	A27	L-T-A27	A44
R-L-A45	$6*S-A16-4*T$	$A11+A8-A5+(7/2)*S+2*M-(5/2)*T$	T-S-A8	$A15+A16+A10+A9+(7/2)*T-(11/2)*S+A5-2*M-A11$	T-S-A9	T-S-A10	T-S-A15	A28	L-T-A28	A45
R-L-A46	A18	$(5*T-3*M)/2-L+A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*S-A8-A24+A23$	A19	A20	$(9*L+3*M)/2-6*T-2*A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*S+A8+A24-A23-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A21	A22	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L	A46
$2*A47-A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46$	L-T-A18	$2*L+(3*M-7*T)/2-A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*S+A8+A24-A23$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$5*T-(7*L+3*M)/2+2*A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*S-A8-A24+A23+A19+A20+A21+A22$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2	$R-L-2*A47+A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46$
$9*L-8*R+A32+A31+A30-A47+A36+A35+A34+A33+A38+A37$	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	A47

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 9 having a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at the upper-left corner. It is again embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 5 having a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×7 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. To avoid decimal entries the pairs (M, S) and (T, L) should be multiple of 2. The magic square of order 3 should also be multiple of 3. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.25. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.13:

11	semi Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										107	
	-71	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	-469	153
	-55	39	-13	25	-103	27	29	41	55	21	87	153
	-57	15	19	-3	-1	-28	36	7	57	19	89	153
	-59	-29	-15	5	25	19	-11	51	59	17	91	153
	-61	35	11	13	-9	21	-13	-13	61	15	93	153
	-63	37	48	17	-53	4	7	-15	-94	170	95	153
	-65	31	-40	-9	61	7	4	-9	63	13	97	153
	-67	-83	35	-3	125	-5	-7	-17	65	11	99	153
	-69	45	-88	47	49	109	51	53	38	-183	101	153
	265	31	164	29	27	-33	25	23	-183	38	-233	153
	455	-37	-39	-41	-43	-45	-47	-49	-51	-53	103	153
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153

The magic square given in Example 2.25 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								121
	39	-13	25	-103	27	29	41	55	21	121
	15	19	-3	-1	-28	36	7	57	19	121
	-29	-15	5	25	19	-11	51	59	17	121
	35	11	13	-9	21	-13	-13	61	15	121
	37	48	17	-53	4	7	-15	-94	170	121
	31	-40	-9	61	7	4	-9	63	13	121
	-83	35	-3	125	-5	-7	-17	65	11	121
	45	-88	47	49	109	51	53	38	-183	121
	31	164	29	27	-33	25	23	-183	38	121
	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121	121

7	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							-19
	39	-13	25	-103	27	29	41	45	
	15	19	-3	-1	-28	36	7	45	
	-29	-15	5	25	19	-11	51	45	
	35	11	13	-9	21	-13	-13	45	
	37	48	17	-53	4	7	-15	45	
	31	-40	-9	61	7	4	-9	45	
	-83	35	-3	125	-5	-7	-17	45	
	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	

5	mgc						23
	19	-3	-1	-28	36	23	
	-15	5	25	19	-11	23	
	11	13	-9	21	-13	23	
	48	17	-53	4	7	23	
	-40	-9	61	7	4	23	
	23	23	23	23	23	23	

3	mgc				15
	19	-3	-1	15	
	-15	5	25	15	
	11	13	-9	15	
	15	15	15	15	

Example 2.26. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.13:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										209
	-65	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	-419	209
	-49	39	-49	25	-49	27	29	41	55	53	87	209
	-51	5	19	-3	-1	5	25	13	57	51	89	209
	-53	-61	-15	5	25	19	11	79	59	49	91	209
	-55	35	11	13	-9	21	9	-17	61	47	93	209
	-57	37	37	17	-9	15	-15	-19	18	90	95	209
	-59	31	-7	13	39	-15	15	-13	63	45	97	209
	-61	-23	67	-7	67	-9	-11	-21	65	43	99	209
	-63	45	-137	47	49	270	51	53	54	-261	101	209
	265	63	245	61	59	-162	57	55	-261	54	-227	209
	457	-31	-33	-35	-37	-39	-41	-43	-45	-47	103	209
	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209	209

The above Example 2.26 is obtained by applying the condition $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. The extra condition $R := \frac{7}{5} \times L$ is applied to bring a **semi-magic** square of order 7 to a magic square. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								171
	39	-49	25	-49	27	29	41	55	53	171
	5	19	-3	-1	5	25	13	57	51	171
	-61	-15	5	25	19	11	79	59	49	171
	35	11	13	-9	21	9	-17	61	47	171
	37	37	17	-9	15	-15	-19	18	90	171
	31	-7	13	39	-15	15	-13	63	45	171
	-23	67	-7	67	-9	-11	-21	65	43	171
	45	-137	47	49	270	51	53	54	-261	171
	63	245	61	59	-162	57	55	-261	54	171
	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						63
	39	-49	25	-49	27	29	41	63
	5	19	-3	-1	5	25	13	63
	-61	-15	5	25	19	11	79	63
	35	11	13	-9	21	9	-17	63
	37	37	17	-9	15	-15	-19	63
	31	-7	13	39	-15	15	-13	63
	-23	67	-7	67	-9	-11	-21	63
	63	63	63	63	63	63	63	63

5	mgc						45
	19	-3	-1	5	25	45	
	-15	5	25	19	11	45	
	11	13	-9	21	9	45	
	37	17	-9	15	-15	45	
	-7	13	39	-15	15	45	
	45	45	45	45	45	45	

3	mgc				15
	19	-3	-1	15	
	-15	5	25	15	
	11	13	-9	15	
	15	15	15	15	

Result 2.14. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A50	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	L+A50-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41
R-L-A42	A18	T-S+A11+A15-A14	A11	S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	A19	L-S-A21+A22-A11+A7-A2-A5-A15+A27-A1	S-T+A21-A22+A11-A7+A2+A5+A15-A27+A1	A42
R-L-A43	5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18	A27	L-T-A27	A43
R-L-A44	A15	3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6	T-S-A15	A28	L-T-A28	A44
R-L-A45	A16	A5	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-A5	T-S-A16	A29	L-T-A29	A45
R-L-A46	A17	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	T-S-A17	(5*L-7*T)/2+ A21-A22+S+A11-A7+A2+A5+A15-2*A27+A1-A28-A29-A30-A31	(5*T-3*L)/2-A21+A22-S-A11+A7-A2-A5-A15+2*A27-A1+A28+A29+A30+A31	A46
R-L-A47	A14	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	T-S-A14	A30	L-T-A30	A47
R-L-A48	6*S-A19-4*T	A14-A11-A15	T-S-A11	A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18	A31	L-T-A31	A48
R-L-A49	A21	A22	A23	A24	7*(L-T)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26	A25	A26	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L	A49
2*A50-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	5*(T-L)/2+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2	R-L-2*A50+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49
A35+A34-A50+A33+A39+A38+A37+A36+A41+9*L+A40-8*R	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	A50

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 9 having a **single-digit bordered** magic squares of orders 7 and 5 at the upper-left corner embedded with a magic square of order 3 in the middle. The magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal width and length. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. To avoid decimal entries the pairs (T, L) should be multiple of 2. Moreover, the magic square of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.27. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.4:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-65	
		-99	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	130	-772	191
		-75	61	73	40	-236	43	46	64	54	-12	133	191
		-78	-122	25	-41	12	31	34	152	88	-46	136	191
		-81	52	67	16	1	4	-27	-22	91	-49	139	191
		-84	55	22	-5	7	19	18	-25	94	-52	142	191
		-87	58	19	10	13	-2	21	-28	-377	419	145	191
		-90	49	-72	81	28	9	15	-19	97	-55	148	191
		-93	-62	-43	-10	266	-13	-16	-31	100	-58	151	191
		-96	70	73	76	79	-318	82	85	21	-35	154	191
		400	-28	-31	-34	-37	360	-40	-43	-35	21	-342	191
		574	-48	-51	-54	-57	-60	-63	-66	-69	-72	157	191
		191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191	191

The magic square given in Example 2.27 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									133
		61	73	40	-236	43	46	64	54	-12	133
		-122	25	-41	12	31	34	152	88	-46	133
		52	67	16	1	4	-27	-22	91	-49	133
		55	22	-5	7	19	18	-25	94	-52	133
		58	19	10	13	-2	21	-28	-377	419	133
		49	-72	81	28	9	15	-19	97	-55	133
		-62	-43	-10	266	-13	-16	-31	100	-58	133
		70	73	76	79	-318	82	85	21	-35	133
		-28	-31	-34	-37	360	-40	-43	-35	21	133
		133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133

7	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							-15
		61	73	40	-236	43	46	64	91
		-122	25	-41	12	31	34	152	91
		52	67	16	1	4	-27	-22	91
		55	22	-5	7	19	18	-25	91
		58	19	10	13	-2	21	-28	91
		49	-72	81	28	9	15	-19	91
		-62	-43	-10	266	-13	-16	-31	91
		91	91	91	91	91	91	91	91

5	semi						-17
		25	-41	12	31	34	61
		67	16	1	4	-27	61
		22	-5	7	19	18	61
		19	10	13	-2	21	61
		-72	81	28	9	15	61
		61	61	61	61	61	61

3	mgc				21
		16	1	4	21
		-5	7	19	21
		10	13	-2	21
		21	21	21	21

Example 2.28. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.14:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										187	
		-123	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	130	-752	187
		-99	61	57	40	-262	43	46	64	100	4	133	187
		-102	-176	25	-41	-14	31	34	190	88	16	136	187
		-105	52	-11	16	1	4	25	-38	91	13	139	187
		-108	55	22	-5	7	19	-8	-41	94	10	142	187
		-111	58	19	10	13	-2	-5	-44	-206	310	145	187
		-114	49	-20	55	28	-17	-11	-35	97	7	148	187
		-117	-50	-43	-26	276	-29	-32	-47	100	4	151	187
		-120	70	73	76	79	-101	82	85	52	-263	154	187
		400	34	31	28	25	205	22	19	-263	52	-366	187
		786	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-90	-93	-96	157	187
		187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187

The above Example 2.28 is obtained by applying the condition $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. It includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
		61	57	40	-262	43	46	64	100	4	153	
		-176	25	-41	-14	31	34	190	88	16	153	
		52	-11	16	1	4	25	-38	91	13	153	
		55	22	-5	7	19	-8	-41	94	10	153	
		58	19	10	13	-2	-5	-44	-206	310	153	
		49	-20	55	28	-17	-11	-35	97	7	153	
		-50	-43	-26	276	-29	-32	-47	100	4	153	
		70	73	76	79	-101	82	85	52	-263	153	
		34	31	28	25	205	22	19	-263	52	153	
		153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							49
		61	57	40	-262	43	46	64	49
		-176	25	-41	-14	31	34	190	49
		52	-11	16	1	4	25	-38	49
		55	22	-5	7	19	-8	-41	49
		58	19	10	13	-2	-5	-44	49
		49	-20	55	28	-17	-11	-35	49
		-50	-43	-26	276	-29	-32	-47	49
		49	49	49	49	49	49	49	49

5	mgc						35
		25	-41	-14	31	34	35
		-11	16	1	4	25	35
		22	-5	7	19	-8	35
		19	10	13	-2	-5	35
		-20	55	28	-17	-11	35
		35	35	35	35	35	35

3	mgc				21
		16	1	4	21
		-5	7	19	21
		10	13	-2	21
		21	21	21	21

Result 2.15. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-3*M-A53	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	3*M+A53-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44
R-3*M-A45	A1	M-A1-A3	A3	A5	M-A5-A7	A7	A9	M-A9-A11	A11	A45
R-3*M-A46	M-A1-A2	A1+A2+A3+A4-M	M-A3-A4	M-A5-A6	A5+A6+A7+A8-M	M-A7-A8	M-A9-A10	3*A16+4*A1+2*A2+2*A3+4*A4+3*A18+4*A31+2*A32+2*A33+4*A34-2*A25-A23-2*A24-A26-A10-A11-7*M	A11+A9+2*A10-3*A16-4*A1-2*A2-2*A3-4*A4+7*M-3*A18-4*A31-2*A32-2*A33-4*A34+2*A25+A23+2*A24+A26	A46
R-3*M-A47	A2	M-A2-A4	A4	A6	M-A6-A8	A8	A10	A10+2*A11+A9-3*A16-4*A1-2*A2-2*A3-4*A4+7*M-3*A18-4*A31-2*A32-2*A33-4*A34+2*A25+A23+2*A24+A26	3*A16+4*A1+2*A2+2*A3+4*A4+3*A18+4*A31+2*A32+2*A33+4*A34-2*A25-A23-2*A24-A26-2*A11-A9-2*A10-6*M	A47
R-3*M-A48	A12	M-A12-A14	A14	A16	M-A16-A17	A17	A19	M-A19-A21	A21	A48
R-3*M-A49	M-A12-A13	A12+A13+A14+A15-M	M-A14-A15	A16+2*A1+A2+A3+2*A4+A17+2*A18+2*A31+A32+A33+2*A34-5*M	5*M-A18-2*A31-A32-A33-2*A34-A16-2*A1-A2-A3-2*A4	M-A17-A18	M-A19-A20	A19+A20+A21+A22-M	M-A21-A22	A49
R-3*M-A50	A13	M-A13-A15	A15	6*M-2*A16-A17-2*A18-2*A31-A32-A33-2*A34-2*A1-A2-A3-2*A4	2*A1+A2+A3+2*A4+2*A16+A17+A18+2*A31+A32+A33+2*A34-5*M	A18	A20	M-A20-A22	A22	A50
R-3*M-A51	A23	M-A23-A25	A25	A27	M-A27-A29	A29	A31	M-A31-A33	A33	A51
R-3*M-A52	M-A23-A24	A23+A24+A25+A26-M	M-A25-A26	M-A27-A28	A27+A28+A29+A30-M	M-A29-A30	M-A31-A32	A31+A32+A33+A34-M	M-A33-A34	A52
2*A53-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51+A52	A24	M-A24-A26	A26	A28	M-A28-A30	A30	A32	M-A32-A34	A34	R-3*M-2*A53+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51-A52
27*M+A43+A44+A41+A42+A38+A39+A40+A36+A37-8*R-A53	R-3*M-A36	R-3*M-A37	R-3*M-A38	R-3*M-A39	R-3*M-A40	R-3*M-A41	R-3*M-A42	R-3*M-A43	R-3*M-A44	A53

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with a **block-wise** magic squares of order 9 having nine equal sums **semi-magic** magic squares of order 3. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the condition given in (1), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$. The letter M, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 9 and 11 respectively, where $L = 3 \times M$. The equal sums blocks of order 3 as **semi-magic** squares is considered to avoid considering magic square of order 3 as multiple of 3. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Result 2.16. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A50	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	L+A50-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41
R-L-A42	L-T-A31	T-L-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	A42
R-L-A43	L-T-A24	(T-S)/2-A12	A14	A10+A11-(T-S)/4	(T-S)/2-A10	(T-S)/2-A11	A9	(5*S-T)/4+A12-A14-A9	A24	A43
R-L-A44	L-T-A25	A13	A12	3*(T-S)/4-A10-A11	A10	A11	(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A14+A9	(5*S-T)/2-A13-A14-A9	A25	A44
R-L-A45	L-T-A26	A15+A16-(T-S)/4	3*(T-S)/4-A15-A16	A1+A2-S/3	2*S/3-A2	2*S/3-A1	3*(T-S)/4-A7-A8	A7+A8-(T-S)/4	A26	A45
R-L-A46	L-T-A27	(T-S)/2-A15	A15	4*S/3-2*A1-A2	S/3	2*A1+A2-2*S/3	A7	(T-S)/2-A7	A27	A46
R-L-A47	L-T-A28	(T-S)/2-A16	A16	A1	A2	S-A1-A2	A8	(T-S)/2-A8	A28	A47
R-L-A48	L-T-A29	A14-A6+A9	(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9	3*(T-S)/4-A4-A5	A4	A5	(5*S-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6	A6	A29	A48
R-L-A49	L-T-A30	(5*S-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9	(5*S-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13	A4+A5-(T-S)/4	(T-S)/2-A4	(T-S)/2-A5	A14+A13-A6	T-3*S-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6	A30	A49
2*A50-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49	8*T-7*L+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24	2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31	R-L-2*A50+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49
A35+A34-A50+A33+A39+A38+A37+A36+A41+9*L+A40-8*R	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	A50

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of orders 11 and 9 embedded with a **double-digit bordered** magic squares of order 7 having a magic square of order 3 in the middle. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the conditions given in (1) and (2), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$. The letter M, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. To avoid **decimal** entries we must have the pairs (T, L) and (L, R) as multiple of 2. Also magic square of order 3 should be multiple of 3. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.31. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.16:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-229
21	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-263	181	
29	-32	149	28	29	30	31	32	33	-200	52	181	
28	-25	7	24	27	9	8	19	-3	34	53	181	
27	-26	23	22	2.5	20	21	32	-29	35	54	181	
26	-27	37	-8	12	10	11	8.5	21	36	55	181	
25	-28	4	25	10	11	12	17	12	37	56	181	
24	-29	3	26	11	12	10	18	11	38	57	181	
23	-30	27	39	15	14	15	-34	16	39	58	181	
22	-31	-9.5	-37	15	15	14	31	63	40	59	181	
141	328	-140	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	41	-60	181	
-185	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	31	30	60	181	
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	

The magic square given in Example 2.31 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								219
-32	149	28	29	30	31	32	33	-200	100	
-25	7	24	27	9	8	19	-3	34	100	
-26	23	22	2.5	20	21	32	-29	35	100	
-27	37	-8	12	10	11	8.5	21	36	100	
-28	4	25	10	11	12	17	12	37	100	
-29	3	26	11	12	10	18	11	38	100	
-30	27	39	15	14	15	-34	16	39	100	
-31	-9.5	-37	15	15	14	31	63	40	100	
328	-140	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	41	100	
100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						91
7	24	27	9	8	19	-3	91	
23	22	2.5	20	21	32	-29	91	
37	-8	12	10	11	8.5	21	91	
4	25	10	11	12	17	12	91	
3	26	11	12	10	18	11	91	
27	39	15	14	15	-34	16	91	
-10	-37	15	15	14	31	63	91	
91	91	91	91	91	91	91	91	

3	mgc				33
12	10	11		33	
10	11	12		33	
11	12	10		33	
33	33	33		33	

Example 2.32. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.16:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										187
	-26	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-210	187
	-18	-7	124	28	29	30	31	32	33	-147	52	187
	-19	0	18	24	21	20	19	19	-2	34	53	187
	-20	-1	23	22	19	20	21	42	-28	35	54	187
	-21	-2	31	9	10	14	15	25	15	36	55	187
	-22	-3	15	25	18	13	8	17	23	37	56	187
	-23	-4	14	26	11	12	16	18	22	38	57	187
	-24	-5	27	49	31	14	15	-33	16	39	58	187
	-25	-6	-9	-36	9	26	25	31	73	40	59	187
	141	181	-90	6	5	4	3	2	1	41	-107	187
	244	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	60	187
	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187	187

The above Example 2.32 is obtained by applying the conditions $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									153
	-7	124	28	29	30	31	32	33	-147	153	
	0	18	24	21	20	19	19	-2	34	153	
	-1	23	22	19	20	21	42	-28	35	153	
	-2	31	9	10	14	15	25	15	36	153	
	-3	15	25	18	13	8	17	23	37	153	
	-4	14	26	11	12	16	18	22	38	153	
	-5	27	49	31	14	15	-33	16	39	153	
	-6	-9	-36	9	26	25	31	73	40	153	
	181	-90	6	5	4	3	2	1	41	153	
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							119
	18	24	21	20	19	19	-2	119	
	23	22	19	20	21	42	-28	119	
	31	9	10	14	15	25	15	119	
	15	25	18	13	8	17	23	119	
	14	26	11	12	16	18	22	119	
	27	49	31	14	15	-33	16	119	
	-9	-36	9	26	25	31	73	119	
	119	119	119	119	119	119	119	119	

3	mgc				39
	10	14	15	39	
	18	13	8	39	
	11	12	16	39	
	39	39	39	39	

Result 2.17. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A68	A51	A52	A53	A54	A55	A56	A57	A58	A59	L+A68-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59
R-L-A60	L-T-A49	T-A41-A40-A39-A38-A37-A36-L+2*A49+A48+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	L-A49-A48-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42	A60
R-L-A61	L-T-A42	T+A16+A30+A12-A24+A26-A20-A19-A23+A8-A22-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8+A22+A21-A16-A30-A12	A42	A61
R-L-A62	L-T-A43	A6	A7	A19+A20+A21+A22+A23+A24-A27-A31-A2-A10-A15	A24+A28+A27+A25+A20+A19+A29+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A2+A1-A34-3*A16-A32-A30-A12-A11-A10	A8	A9	T+A34+3*A16+A15+A32+A31+A30+A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A28-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A9-A6-A22-A5-A4-A1-A21	A43	A62
R-L-A63	L-T-A44	A24-A26-A25+A20+A23-A8-A6+A22+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A16-A14-2*A30-A12	A18-A16+A14+A33+A30-A13-A12-A11-2*A10+A25+A19+A23+A8-A7+A6-A22+A5-A34	A10	A11	A12	A13	T+A34-A18+2*A16-A33+A30+A12+A10-A24+A26-A20-A19-2*A23+A7-2*A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21	A44	A63
R-L-A64	L-T-A45	A14	A34-A18-A17-2*A16-A15-A14-A30+A13-A12+2*A24-A26+A20+A19+A29+A23+A9-A8+A22+A21	A15	A16	A17	A18	T-A34+A16+A30-A13+A12-2*A24+A26-A20-A19-A29-A23-A9+A8-A22-A21	A45	A64
R-L-A65	L-T-A46	A19	A20	T-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23-A24	A21	A22	A23	A24	A46	A65
R-L-A66	L-T-A47	A25	A26	A27	T+A34+2*A16+A30+A12+A10-A24-A28-A27-A25-A20-A19-A29-A23+A8+A7-A5-A4-A3-A2-A1-A21	A28	A29	A24-A26+A20+A19+A23-A8-A7+A5+A4+A3+A2+A1+A21-A34-2*A16-A30-A12-A10	A47	A66
R-L-A67	L-T-A48	A30	T+A17+3*A16+A15-A33-A9+2*A12+A11+2*A10-2*A24-A25-2*A20-2*A19-A29-2*A23-A6-A5-A1-A21	A31	A32	A33	A34	2*A24+A25+2*A20+2*A19+A29+2*A23+A9+A6+A5+A1+A21-A34-A17-3*A16-A15-A32-A31-A30-2*A12-A11-2*A10	A48	A67
2*A68-A51-A52-A53-A54-A55-A56-A57-A58-A59+A60+A61+A62+A63+A64+A65+A66+A67	8*T+A49+A48+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42-7*L	2*L-2*T+A41+A40+A39+A38+A37+A36-2*A49-A48-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42	L-T-A36	L-T-A37	L-T-A38	L-T-A39	L-T-A40	L-T-A41	A49	R-L-2*A68+A51+A52+A53+A54+A55+A56+A57+A58+A59-A60-A61-A62-A63-A64-A65-A66-A67
9*L-8*R+A59+A57+A58+A56+A55+A54+A53+A52+A51-A68	R-L-A51	R-L-A52	R-L-A53	R-L-A54	R-L-A55	R-L-A56	R-L-A57	R-L-A58	R-L-A59	A68

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of orders 11 and 9 embedded with a magic squares of order 7. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the conditions given in (1) and (2), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$. The letter T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 7, 9 and 11 respectively. To avoid **decimal** entries we must have the pairs (T, L) and (L, R) as multiple of 2. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.33. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.17:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-199
-133	160	163	166	169	172	175	178	181	184	-1162	253	
-109	-104	517	115	118	121	124	127	130	-973	187	253	
-112	-83	-73	10	13	16	19	22	118	133	190	253	
-115	-86	25	28	139	52	-184	31	34	136	193	253	
-118	-89	-119	145	37	40	43	-67	46	139	196	253	
-121	-92	49	205	52	55	58	61	-355	142	199	253	
-124	-95	64	67	-304	70	73	76	79	145	202	253	
-127	-98	82	85	88	-211	91	-104	94	148	205	253	
-130	-101	97	-415	100	103	25	106	109	151	208	253	
454	923	-467	-65	-68	-71	-74	-77	-80	154	-376	253	
888	-82	-85	-88	-91	-94	-97	-100	-103	-106	211	253	
253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	

The magic square given in Example 2.33 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								75														
-104	517	115	118	121	124	127	130	-973	175	7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							125					
-83	-73	10	13	16	19	22	118	133	175			-73	10	13	16	19	22	118	125					
-86	25	28	139	52	-184	31	34	136	175			25	28	139	52	-184	31	34	125					
-89	-119	145	37	40	43	-67	46	139	175			-119	145	37	40	43	-67	46	125					
-92	49	205	52	55	58	61	-355	142	175			49	205	52	55	58	61	-355	125					
-95	64	67	-304	70	73	76	79	145	175			64	67	-304	70	73	76	79	125					
-98	82	85	88	-211	91	-104	94	148	175			82	85	88	-211	91	-104	94	125					
-101	97	-415	100	103	25	106	109	151	175			97	-415	100	103	25	106	109	125					
923	-467	-65	-68	-71	-74	-77	-80	154	175			125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125					
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175															

Example 2.34. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.17:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										198
	-175	160	163	166	169	172	175	178	181	184	-1175	198
	-151	-118	531	115	118	121	124	127	130	-986	187	198
	-154	-97	-72	10	13	16	19	22	118	133	190	198
	-157	-100	25	28	139	52	-183	31	34	136	193	198
	-160	-103	-119	145	37	40	43	-66	46	139	196	198
	-163	-106	49	205	52	55	58	61	-354	142	199	198
	-166	-109	64	67	-303	70	73	76	79	145	202	198
	-169	-112	82	85	88	-210	91	-104	94	148	205	198
	-172	-115	97	-414	100	103	25	106	109	151	208	198
	454	1022	-495	-79	-82	-85	-88	-91	-94	154	-418	198
	1211	-124	-127	-130	-133	-136	-139	-142	-145	-148	211	198
	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198

The above Example 2.20 is obtained by applying the conditions $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								162
	-118	531	115	118	121	124	127	130	-986	162
	-97	-72	10	13	16	19	22	118	133	162
	-100	25	28	139	52	-183	31	34	136	162
	-103	-119	145	37	40	43	-66	46	139	162
	-106	49	205	52	55	58	61	-354	142	162
	-109	64	67	-303	70	73	76	79	145	162
	-112	82	85	88	-210	91	-104	94	148	162
	-115	97	-414	100	103	25	106	109	151	162
	1022	-495	-79	-82	-85	-88	-91	-94	154	162
	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						126
	-72	10	13	16	19	22	118	126
	25	28	139	52	-183	31	34	126
	-119	145	37	40	43	-66	46	126
	49	205	52	55	58	61	-354	126
	64	67	-303	70	73	76	79	126
	82	85	88	-210	91	-104	94	126
	97	-414	100	103	25	106	109	126
	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126

Result 2.18. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

R-L-A50	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	L+A50-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41
R-L-A42	L-T-A31	T-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18-L+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	A42
R-L-A43	L-T-A24	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	A24	A43
R-L-A44	L-T-A25	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	A25	A44
R-L-A45	L-T-A26	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13	3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16	A26	A45
R-L-A46	L-T-A27	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15	A27	A46
R-L-A47	L-T-A28	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16	A28	A47
R-L-A48	L-T-A29	T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13	A10	A7+A8+3*T/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13-3*S/2	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A29	A48
R-L-A49	L-T-A30	A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	S/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13-T/2	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A30	A49
2*A50-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49	8*T+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-7*L	2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31	R-L-2*A50+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49
A35+A34-A50+A33+A39+A38+A37+A36+A41+9*L+A40-8*R	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	A50

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of orders 11 and 9 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 7. It contains a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 at the upper-left corner. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the conditions given in (1) and (2), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$. The magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal width and length. The letter S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.35. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.18:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-672	
		138	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-321	240
		146	-258	514	28	29	30	31	32	33	-397	52	240
		145	-112	11	12	50	13	14	23	-3	34	53	240
		144	-113	23	15	2	16	44	24	-4	35	54	240
		143	-114	7	48	17	25	3	-48	68	36	55	240
		142	-115	19	13	8	39	21	25	-5	37	56	240
		141	-116	40	12	23	7	18	26	-6	38	57	240
		140	-117	6	20	-19	21	22	10	60	39	58	240
		139	-118	14	0	39	-1	-2	60	10	40	59	240
		141	1105	-592	-106	-107	-108	-109	-110	-111	180	57	240
		-1179	155	154	153	152	151	150	149	148	147	60	240
		240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

The magic square given in Example 2.35 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									828
		-258	514	28	29	30	31	32	33	-397	42
		-112	11	12	50	13	14	23	-3	34	42
		-113	23	15	2	16	44	24	-4	35	42
		-114	7	48	17	25	3	-48	68	36	42
		-115	19	13	8	39	21	25	-5	37	42
		-116	40	12	23	7	18	26	-6	38	42
		-117	6	20	-19	21	22	10	60	39	42
		-118	14	0	39	-1	-2	60	10	40	42
		1105	-592	-106	-107	-108	-109	-110	-111	180	42
		42	42	42	42	42	42	42	42	42	42

7	mgc								120
		11	12	50	13	14	23	-3	120
		23	15	2	16	44	24	-4	120
		7	48	17	25	3	-48	68	120
		19	13	8	39	21	25	-5	120
		40	12	23	7	18	26	-6	120
		6	20	-19	21	22	10	60	120
		14	0	39	-1	-2	60	10	120
		120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

5	mgc	100	100	100	100	100		
		100	11	12	50	13	14	100
		100	23	15	2	16	44	100
		100	7	48	17	25	3	100
		100	19	13	8	39	21	100
			40	12	23	7	18	100
			100	100	100	100	100	100

Example 2.36. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.18:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										231
	-18	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-174	231
	-10	1	116	28	29	30	31	32	33	-111	52	231
	-11	8	11	12	51	13	14	23	23	34	53	231
	-12	7	23	15	2	16	45	24	22	35	54	231
	-13	6	7	49	17	25	3	17	29	36	55	231
	-14	5	19	13	8	40	21	25	21	37	56	231
	-15	4	41	12	23	7	18	26	20	38	57	231
	-16	3	32	20	20	21	22	23	9	39	58	231
	-17	2	14	26	26	25	24	9	23	40	59	231
	141	153	-74	14	13	12	11	10	9	41	-99	231
	216	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	60	231
	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231

The above Example 2.36 is obtained by applying the conditions $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									189
	1	116	28	29	30	31	32	33	-111	189	
	8	11	12	51	13	14	23	23	34	189	
	7	23	15	2	16	45	24	22	35	189	
	6	7	49	17	25	3	17	29	36	189	
	5	19	13	8	40	21	25	21	37	189	
	4	41	12	23	7	18	26	20	38	189	
	3	32	20	20	21	22	23	9	39	189	
	2	14	26	26	25	24	9	23	40	189	
	153	-74	14	13	12	11	10	9	41	189	
	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	

7	mgc								147
	11	12	51	13	14	23	23	147	
	23	15	2	16	45	24	22	147	
	7	49	17	25	3	17	29	147	
	19	13	8	40	21	25	21	147	
	41	12	23	7	18	26	20	147	
	32	20	20	21	22	23	9	147	
	14	26	26	25	24	9	23	147	
	147	147	147	147	147	147	147	147	

5	mgc	101	101	101	101	101	
	101	11	12	51	13	14	101
	101	23	15	2	16	45	101
	101	7	49	17	25	3	101
	101	19	13	8	40	21	101
		41	12	23	7	18	101
		101	101	101	101	101	101

Result 2.19. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A47	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	L+A48-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39
R-L-A40	L-T-A29	T-A21-A20-A19-A18-A17-A16-L+2*A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22	A16	A17	A18	A19	A20	A21	L-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22	A40
R-L-A41	L-T-A22	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6	A5+A6-(S-M)/2	A11	T-S-A11	A22	A41
R-L-A42	L-T-A23	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12	A23	A42
R-L-A43	L-T-A24	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13	A24	A43
R-L-A44	L-T-A25	A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2	A4	A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6	(S-M)/2	2*M-S	5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14	3*(S-T)/2+A11+A12+A13+A14	A25	A44
R-L-A45	L-T-A26	A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4	S-M-A4	2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6	2*M-S	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14	A26	A45
R-L-A46	L-T-A27	T-3*S/2-M/2+A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11	A8	A9	3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11-A9-A10	A10	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A27	A46
R-L-A47	L-T-A28	S/2+M/2-A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	2*A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11+A9+A10-T/2-M/2	T-S-A10	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A28	A47
2*A48-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47	8*T+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22-7*L	2*L-2*T+A21+A20+A19+A18+A17+A16-2*A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22	L-T-A16	L-T-A17	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	A29	R-L-2*A48+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47
9*L-8*R+A33+A32+A31-A48+A37+A36+A35+A34+A39+A38	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	A48

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of orders 11 and 9 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 7 and 5. It contains a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the conditions given in (1) and (2), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$. The magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×5 are of equal width and length in each case. The letter M, S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. To avoid **decimal** entries we must have the pair (S, T) as multiple of 2. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.37. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.19:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										366
	-30	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-141	252
	-22	15	102	28	29	30	31	32	33	-78	52	252
	-23	22	5	24	25	50	4	21	37	34	53	252
	-24	21	38	18	-2	15	39	22	36	35	54	252
	-25	20	11	12	31	16	38	23	35	36	55	252
	-26	19	10	14	57	27	0	55	3	37	56	252
	-27	18	44	40	-3	0	27	24	34	38	57	252
	-28	17	31	18	19	57	20	29	-8	39	58	252
	-29	16	27	40	39	1	38	-8	29	40	59	252
	141	74	-46	28	27	26	25	24	23	41	-111	252
	345	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	60	252
	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252	252

The magic square given in Example 2.37 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									162
	15	102	28	29	30	31	32	33	-78	222	
	22	5	24	25	50	4	21	37	34	222	
	21	38	18	-2	15	39	22	36	35	222	
	20	11	12	31	16	38	23	35	36	222	
	19	10	14	57	27	0	55	3	37	222	
	18	44	40	-3	0	27	24	34	38	222	
	17	31	18	19	57	20	29	-8	39	222	
	16	27	40	39	1	38	-8	29	40	222	
	74	-46	28	27	26	25	24	23	41	222	
	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	

7	mgc								166
	5	24	25	50	4	21	37	166	
	38	18	-2	15	39	22	36	166	
	11	12	31	16	38	23	35	166	
	10	14	57	27	0	55	3	166	
	44	40	-3	0	27	24	34	166	
	31	18	19	57	20	29	-8	166	
	27	40	39	1	38	-8	29	166	
	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	

5	mgc						108
	5	24	25	50	4	108	
	38	18	-2	15	39	108	
	11	12	31	16	38	108	
	10	14	57	27	0	108	
	44	40	-3	0	27	108	
	108	108	108	108	108	108	

3	mgc				54
	5	24	25	54	
	38	18	-2	54	
	11	12	31	54	
	54	54	54	54	

Example 2.38. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.19:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										220
	-20	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-183	220
	-12	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-120	52	220
	-13	6	5	24	25	50	4	21	11	34	53	220
	-14	5	38	18	-2	15	39	22	10	35	54	220
	-15	4	11	12	31	16	38	23	9	36	55	220
	-16	3	10	14	57	27	0	-10	42	37	56	220
	-17	2	44	40	-3	0	27	24	8	38	57	220
	-18	1	5	18	19	18	20	16	44	39	58	220
	-19	0	27	14	13	14	12	44	16	40	59	220
	141	160	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	-101	220
	223	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	60	220
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

The above Example 2.38 is obtained by applying the conditions $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									180
	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-120	180	
	6	5	24	25	50	4	21	11	34	180	
	5	38	18	-2	15	39	22	10	35	180	
	4	11	12	31	16	38	23	9	36	180	
	3	10	14	57	27	0	-10	42	37	180	
	2	44	40	-3	0	27	24	8	38	180	
	1	5	18	19	18	20	16	44	39	180	
	0	27	14	13	14	12	44	16	40	180	
	160	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	180	
	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT							140
	5	24	25	50	4	21	11	140	
	38	18	-2	15	39	22	10	140	
	11	12	31	16	38	23	9	140	
	10	14	57	27	0	-10	42	140	
	44	40	-3	0	27	24	8	140	
	5	18	19	18	20	16	44	140	
	27	14	13	14	12	44	16	140	
	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	

5	mgc						108
	5	24	25	50	4	108	
	38	18	-2	15	39	108	
	11	12	31	16	38	108	
	10	14	57	27	0	108	
	44	40	-3	0	27	108	
	108	108	108	108	108	108	

3	mgc				54
	5	24	25	54	
	38	18	-2	54	
	11	12	31	54	
	54	54	54	54	

Result 2.20. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A51	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	L+A51-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42
R-L-A43	L-T-A32	T-A24-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-L+2*A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	L-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25	A43
R-L-A44	L-T-A25	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	A14	T-S-A14	A25	A44
R-L-A45	L-T-A26	3*S-4*M-A6+A9-2*A7-A8+A2+A1-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*M-2*S+A4+2*A7+A8-A2-A1-A9+A6	A15	T-S-A15	A26	A45
R-L-A46	L-T-A27	2*A7+A8-A2-A1	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-2*A7-A8+A2+A1	(5/2)*T-(5/2)*S-A17-A16-A15-A14	(3/2)*S-(3/2)*T+A14+A15+A16+A17	A27	A46
R-L-A47	L-T-A28	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	A16	T-S-A16	A28	A47
R-L-A48	L-T-A29	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	A17	T-S-A17	A29	A48
R-L-A49	L-T-A30	T-S-A7+A11-A8+A15-A14	A11	A7+A8+(3/2)*T-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14-(3/2)*S	A12	A13	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A30	A49
R-L-A50	L-T-A31	A7-A11+A8-A15+A14	T-S-A11	(1/2)*S+A13+A12+2*A11-A7-A8+A15-A14-(1/2)*T	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A31	A50
2*A51-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50	8*T+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25-7*L	2*L-2*T+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19-2*A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	A32	R-L-2*A51+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50
9*L-8*R+A42+A41+A40+A39+A38+A37+A36+A35+A34-A51	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	A51

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of orders 11 and 9 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 7. It contains a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 5 embedded with a magic square of order 3 in the middle. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the conditions given in (1) and (2), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$. The magic rectangles of order 2×5 are of equal width and length. The letter M, S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. To avoid **decimal** entries we must have the pair (S, T) as multiple of 2. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.39. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.20:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-204
	-3	77	79	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	-432	330
	13	-23	239	47	49	51	53	55	57	-306	95	330
	11	-9	21	-17	44	25	27	37	35	59	97	330
	9	-11	110	13	9	11	-43	39	33	61	99	330
	7	-13	47	9	11	13	20	20	52	63	101	330
	5	-15	17	11	13	9	50	41	31	65	103	330
	3	-17	-95	84	23	42	46	43	29	67	105	330
	1	-19	57	31	24	33	35	36	-44	69	107	330
	-1	-21	15	41	48	39	37	-44	36	71	109	330
	273	350	-189	3	1	-1	-3	-5	-7	73	-165	330
	12	31	29	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	111	330
	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330

The magic square given in Example 2.39 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										216
	-23	239	47	49	51	53	55	57	-306	222		
	-9	21	-17	44	25	27	37	35	59	222		
	-11	110	13	9	11	-43	39	33	61	222		
	-13	47	9	11	13	20	20	52	63	222		
	-15	17	11	13	9	50	41	31	65	222		
	-17	-95	84	23	42	46	43	29	67	222		
	-19	57	31	24	33	35	36	-44	69	222		
	-21	15	41	48	39	37	-44	36	71	222		
	350	-189	3	1	-1	-3	-5	-7	73	222		
	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	222	222		

7	mgc								172
	21	-17	44	25	27	37	35	172	
	110	13	9	11	-43	39	33	172	
	47	9	11	13	20	20	52	172	
	17	11	13	9	50	41	31	172	
	-95	84	23	42	46	43	29	172	
	57	31	24	33	35	36	-44	172	
	15	41	48	39	37	-44	36	172	
	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	

5	semi						-35
	21	-17	44	25	27	100	
	110	13	9	11	-43	100	
	47	9	11	13	20	100	
	17	11	13	9	50	100	
	-95	84	23	42	46	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	

3	mgc				33
	13	9	11	33	
	9	11	13	33	
	11	13	9	33	
	33	33	33	33	

Example 2.40. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.20:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										330	
		-51	77	79	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	-384	330
		-35	-13	229	47	49	51	53	55	57	-258	95	330
		-37	1	21	-14	1	25	27	37	113	59	97	330
		-39	-1	-22	12	11	13	46	39	111	61	99	330
		-41	-3	47	13	12	11	-23	215	-65	63	101	330
		-43	-5	17	11	13	12	7	41	109	65	103	330
		-45	-7	-3	38	23	-1	3	43	107	67	105	330
		-47	-9	135	31	141	33	35	75	-240	69	107	330
		-49	-11	15	119	9	117	115	-240	75	71	109	330
		273	318	-169	13	11	9	7	5	3	73	-213	330
		444	-17	-19	-21	-23	-25	-27	-29	-31	-33	111	330
		330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330

The above Example 2.40 is obtained by applying the conditions $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$ and $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$. An extra condition $S := \frac{5}{3} \times M$ is also applied to bring block of order 5 as a magic square. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										270
		-13	229	47	49	51	53	55	57	-258		270
		1	21	-14	1	25	27	37	113	59		270
		-1	-22	12	11	13	46	39	111	61		270
		-3	47	13	12	11	-23	215	-65	63		270
		-5	17	11	13	12	7	41	109	65		270
		-7	-3	38	23	-1	3	43	107	67		270
		-9	135	31	141	33	35	75	-240	69		270
		-11	15	119	9	117	115	-240	75	71		270
		318	-169	13	11	9	7	5	3	73		270
		270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270		270

7	mgc								210
		21	-14	1	25	27	37	113	210
		-22	12	11	13	46	39	111	210
		47	13	12	11	-23	215	-65	210
		17	11	13	12	7	41	109	210
		-3	38	23	-1	3	43	107	210
		135	31	141	33	35	75	-240	210
		15	119	9	117	115	-240	75	210
		210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210

5	mgc						60
		21	-14	1	25	27	60
		-22	12	11	13	46	60
		47	13	12	11	-23	60
		17	11	13	12	7	60
		-3	38	23	-1	3	60
		60	60	60	60	60	60

3	mgc				36
		12	11	13	36
		13	12	11	36
		11	13	12	36
		36	36	36	36

Result 2.21. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A52	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	L+A52-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43
R-L-A44	L-T-A33	T-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21-A20-L+2*A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	A25	L-A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26	A44
R-L-A45	L-T-A26	A17	T-S+A10+A14-A13	A10	S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	A18	A26	A45
R-L-A46	L-T-A27	A14	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	T-S-A14	A27	A46
R-L-A47	L-T-A28	5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	5*S-4*T+A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17	A28	A47
R-L-A48	L-T-A29	A15	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	T-S-A15	A29	A48
R-L-A49	L-T-A30	A16	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	T-S-A16	A30	A49
R-L-A50	L-T-A31	A13	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	T-S-A13	A31	A50
R-L-A51	L-T-A32	6*S-A18-4*T	A13-A10-A14	T-S-A10	A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10+T-2*S+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17	A32	A51
2*A52-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50+A51	8*T+A33+A32+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26-7*L	2*L-2*T+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21+A20-2*A33-A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	A33	R-L-2*A52+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50-A51
9*L-8*R+A41+A42+A43+A37+A38+A39+A40-A52+A35+A36	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	A52

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of orders 11, 9 and 7 embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the conditions given in (1), (1), and (2) and (3), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$, $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$ and $T := \frac{7}{5} \times S$. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.41. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.21:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										412	
		-23	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	-198	220
		-15	-14	135	30	31	32	33	34	35	-135	54	220
		-16	-7	27	53	20	-19	21	22	28	36	55	220
		-17	-8	24	11	12	70	13	14	8	37	56	220
		-18	-9	-57	23	15	2	16	64	89	38	57	220
		-19	-10	25	7	68	17	25	3	7	39	58	220
		-20	-11	26	19	13	8	59	21	6	40	59	220
		-21	-12	23	60	12	23	7	18	9	41	60	220
		-22	-13	84	-21	12	51	11	10	5	42	61	220
		143	265	-106	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	43	-104	220
		248	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	62	220
		220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

The magic square given in Example 2.41 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										362																			
		-14	135	30	31	32	33	34	35	-135	181																				
		-7	27	53	20	-19	21	22	28	36	181		2	semi							232										
		-8	24	11	12	70	13	14	8	37	181				27	53	20	-19	21	22	28	152		5	pan	120	120	120	120	120	
		-9	-57	23	15	2	16	64	89	38	181				24	11	12	70	13	14	8	152			120	11	12	70	13	14	120
		-10	25	7	68	17	25	3	7	39	181				-57	23	15	2	16	64	89	152			120	23	15	2	16	64	120
		-11	26	19	13	8	59	21	6	40	181				25	7	68	17	25	3	7	152			120	7	68	17	25	3	120
		-12	23	60	12	23	7	18	9	41	181				26	19	13	8	59	21	6	152			120	19	13	8	59	21	120
		-13	84	-21	12	51	11	10	5	42	181				23	60	12	23	7	18	9	152				60	12	23	7	18	120
		265	-106	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	43	181				84	-21	12	51	11	10	5	152				120	120	120	120	120	120
		181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181				152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152									

Example 2.42. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.21:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										253
	-16	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	-172	253
	-8	3	118	30	31	32	33	34	35	-109	54	253
	-9	10	27	67	20	-24	21	22	28	36	55	253
	-10	9	24	11	12	65	13	14	22	37	56	253
	-11	8	18	23	15	2	16	59	28	38	57	253
	-12	7	25	7	63	17	25	3	21	39	58	253
	-13	6	26	19	13	8	54	21	20	40	59	253
	-14	5	23	55	12	23	7	18	23	41	60	253
	-15	4	18	-21	26	70	25	24	19	42	61	253
	143	155	-72	16	15	14	13	12	11	43	-97	253
	218	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	62	253
	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253

The above Example 2.42 is obtained by applying the conditions $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$, $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$ and $T := \frac{7}{5} \times S$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										207
	3	118	30	31	32	33	34	35	-109			207
	10	27	67	20	-24	21	22	28	36			207
	9	24	11	12	65	13	14	22	37			207
	8	18	23	15	2	16	59	28	38			207
	7	25	7	63	17	25	3	21	39			207
	6	26	19	13	8	54	21	20	40			207
	5	23	55	12	23	7	18	23	41			207
	4	18	-21	26	70	25	24	19	42			207
	155	-72	16	15	14	13	12	11	43			207
	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207			207

2	mgc											161
	27	67	20	-24	21	22	28					161
	24	11	12	65	13	14	22					161
	18	23	15	2	16	59	28					161
	25	7	63	17	25	3	21					161
	26	19	13	8	54	21	20					161
	23	55	12	23	7	18	23					161
	18	-21	26	70	25	24	19					161
	161	161	161	161	161	161	161					161

5	pan	115	115	115	115	115	
	115	11	12	65	13	14	115
	115	23	15	2	16	59	115
	115	7	63	17	25	3	115
	115	19	13	8	54	21	115
		55	12	23	7	18	115
		115	115	115	115	115	115

Result 2.22. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

R-L-A50	A33	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	L+A50-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41
R-L-A42	L-T-A31	T-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18-L+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	A42
R-L-A43	L-T-A24	A15	T-S+A8+A12-A11	A8	S-A15-A16-A10-A9-2*A8-A12+A11	A9	A10	A16	A24	A43
R-L-A44	L-T-A25	5*T-6*S-A15+A16-A14-A12-A13-A11	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6	A5+A6-(S-M)/2	5*S-4*T+A11+A12+A13+A14-A16+A15	A25	A44
R-L-A45	L-T-A26	A12	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	A5	S-M-A5	T-S-A12	A26	A45
R-L-A46	L-T-A27	A13	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	T-S-A13	A27	A46
R-L-A47	L-T-A28	A14	A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2	A4	A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6	(S-M)/2	2*M-S	T-S-A14	A28	A47
R-L-A48	L-T-A29	A11	A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4	S-M-A4	2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6	2*M-S	(S-M)/2	T-S-A11	A29	A48
R-L-A49	L-T-A30	6*S-A16-4*T	A11-A8-A12	T-S-A8	A15+A16+A10+A9+2*A8+T-2*S+A12-A11	T-S-A9	T-S-A10	T-S-A15	A30	A49
2*A50-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49	8*T+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-7*L	2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31	R-L-2*A50+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49
A35+A34-A50+A33+A39+A38+A37+A36+A41+9*L+A40-8*R	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	A50

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of orders 11, 9 and 7 embedded with a **cornered** magic squares of order 5. It contains a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. It becomes magic square by applying the conditions given in (1), (1), and (2) and (3), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$, $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$ and $T := \frac{7}{5} \times S$. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. To avoid decimal entries we must have the (S,M) as multiple of 2. Moreover, the magic square of order 3 should also be multiple of 3. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.43. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.22:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										360	
		-23	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-167	233
		-15	5	112	28	29	30	31	32	33	-104	52	233
		-16	12	25	49	18	-7	19	20	26	34	53	233
		-17	11	-59	-7	48	49	14	16	89	35	54	233
		-18	10	22	86	30	-26	15	15	8	36	55	233
		-19	9	23	11	12	67	16	14	7	37	56	233
		-20	8	24	22	14	9	15	60	6	38	57	233
		-21	7	21	8	16	21	60	15	9	39	58	233
		-22	6	94	-19	12	37	11	10	5	40	59	233
		141	128	-66	18	17	16	15	14	13	41	-104	233
		263	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	60	233
		233	233	233	233	233	233	233	233	233	233	233	233

The magic square given in Example 2.43 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										264																							
		5	112	28	29	30	31	32	33	-104	196	2	semi								240														
		12	25	49	18	-7	19	20	26	34	196			25	49	18	-7	19	20	26	150	5	mgc						120						
		11	-59	-7	48	49	14	16	89	35	196			-59	-7	48	49	14	16	89	150			-7	48	49	14	16	120	3	mgc				90
		10	22	86	30	-26	15	15	8	36	196			22	86	30	-26	15	15	8	150			86	30	-26	15	15	120			-7	48	49	90
		9	23	11	12	67	16	14	7	37	196			23	11	12	67	16	14	7	150			11	12	67	16	14	120			86	30	-26	90
		8	24	22	14	9	15	60	6	38	196			24	22	14	9	15	60	6	150			22	14	9	15	60	120			11	12	67	90
		7	21	8	16	21	60	15	9	39	196			21	8	16	21	60	15	9	150			8	16	21	60	15	120			90	90	90	90
		6	94	-19	12	37	11	10	5	40	196			94	-19	12	37	11	10	5	150			120	120	120	120	120	120						
		128	-66	18	17	16	15	14	13	41	196			150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150														
		196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196																								

Example 2.44. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.22:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										242
	-16	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-165	242
	-8	3	114	28	29	30	31	32	33	-102	52	242
	-9	10	25	63	18	-17	19	20	26	34	53	242
	-10	9	21	-1	36	37	26	12	23	35	54	242
	-11	8	22	62	24	-14	15	23	22	36	55	242
	-12	7	23	11	12	49	16	22	21	37	56	242
	-13	6	24	18	14	25	19	34	20	38	57	242
	-14	5	21	20	24	13	34	19	23	39	58	242
	-15	4	18	-19	26	61	25	24	19	40	59	242
	141	146	-70	16	15	14	13	12	11	41	-97	242
	209	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	60	242
	242	242	242	242	242	242	242	242	242	242	242	242

The above Example 2.44 is obtained by applying the conditions $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$, $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$ and $T := \frac{7}{5} \times S$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								198
	3	114	28	29	30	31	32	33	-102	198
	10	25	63	18	-17	19	20	26	34	198
	9	21	-1	36	37	26	12	23	35	198
	8	22	62	24	-14	15	23	22	36	198
	7	23	11	12	49	16	22	21	37	198
	6	24	18	14	25	19	34	20	38	198
	5	21	20	24	13	34	19	23	39	198
	4	18	-19	26	61	25	24	19	40	198
	146	-70	16	15	14	13	12	11	41	198
	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198

2	mgc							154
	25	63	18	-17	19	20	26	154
	21	-1	36	37	26	12	23	154
	22	62	24	-14	15	23	22	154
	23	11	12	49	16	22	21	154
	24	18	14	25	19	34	20	154
	21	20	24	13	34	19	23	154
	18	-19	26	61	25	24	19	154
	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

5	mgc						110
	-1	36	37	26	12	110	
	62	24	-14	15	23	110	
	11	12	49	16	22	110	
	18	14	25	19	34	110	
	20	24	13	34	19	110	
	110	110	110	110	110	110	

3	mgc			72
	-1	36	37	72
	62	24	-14	72
	11	12	49	72
	72	72	72	72

Result 2.23. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

R-L-A53	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	L+A53-A36-A37- A38-A39-A40-A41- A42-A43-A44
R-L-A45	L-T-A28	T-L-A34-A33-A32- A31-A30-A29 +2*A28+A27+A26+ A25+A24+A23+ A22+A21	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	L-A28-A27- A26-A25- A24-A23- A22-A21	A45
R-L-A46	L-T-A21	A18	T-S+A11+A15-A14	A11	S-A18-A19-A13- A12-2*A11- A15+A14	A12	A13	A19	A21	A46
R-L-A47	L-T-A22	5*T-6*S-A18+A19- A17-A15-A16-A14	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	5*S-4*T+A14+ A15+A16+A17- A19+A18	A22	A47
R-L-A48	L-T-A23	A15	3*S-4*M-A6+A9- A5-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	L-2*S+A4+A5- A9+A6	T-S-A15	A23	A48
R-L-A49	L-T-A24	A16	A5	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-A5	T-S-A16	A24	A49
R-L-A50	L-T-A25	A17	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	T-S-A17	A25	A50
R-L-A51	L-T-A26	A14	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S- 2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	T-S-A14	A26	A51
R-L-A52	L-T-A27	6*S-A19-4*T	A14-A11-A15	T-S-A11	A18+A19+A13+A1 2+ 2*A11+T- 2*S+A15-A14	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18	A27	A52
2*A53-A36-A37- A38-A39-A40-A41- A42-A43- A44+A45+A46+ A47+A48+A49+A 50+A51+A52	8*T-7*L+A28+ A27+A26+A25 +A24+A23+ A22+A21	2*L-2*T+A34+A33+ A32+A31+A30+A29- 2*A28-A27-A26- A25-A24-A23-A22- A21	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	A28	R-L-2*A53+A36+ A37+A38+A39+ A40+A41+A42+A 43+A44-A45-A46- A47-A48-A49- A50-A51-A52
9*L+A43+A44+A 41+A42+A38+A3 9+A40+A36+A37- 8*R-A53	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	R-L-A44	A53

• **Details:**

It is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of orders 11, 9, 7 and 5 embedded with a magic square of order 3. It is a **semi-magic** square at one diagonal. The letters M, S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. It becomes magic square by applying the conditions given in (1)-(4), i.e., $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$, $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$, $T := \frac{7}{5} \times S$ and $S := \frac{5}{3} \times M$. See below two examples. One is **semi-magic** square, and the second one is magic square.

Example 2.45. Let's consider an example of **semi-magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.23:

11	semi	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										4	
		-33	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	-256	161
		-25	2	25	39	40	41	42	43	44	-145	55	161
		-26	9	28	42	21	-74	22	23	29	31	56	161
		-27	8	-72	16	-12	30	18	19	92	32	57	161
		-28	7	25	91	15	4	5	-44	-5	33	58	161
		-29	6	26	15	-2	8	18	32	-6	34	59	161
		-30	5	27	14	11	12	1	33	-7	35	60	161
		-31	4	24	-65	59	17	29	31	-4	36	61	161
		-32	3	33	-22	-1	94	-2	-3	-8	37	62	161
		144	87	15	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	38	-114	161
		278	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	63	161
		161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161

The magic square given in Example 2.45 includes the following magic and **semi-magic** squares:

9	semi	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-18
		2	25	39	40	41	42	43	44	-145	131	
		9	28	42	21	-74	22	23	29	31	131	
		8	-72	16	-12	30	18	19	92	32	131	
		7	25	91	15	4	5	-44	-5	33	131	
		6	26	15	-2	8	18	32	-6	34	131	
		5	27	14	11	12	1	33	-7	35	131	
		4	24	-65	59	17	29	31	-4	36	131	
		3	33	-22	-1	94	-2	-3	-8	37	131	
		87	15	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	38	131	
		131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	

2	semi								40
		28	42	21	-74	22	23	29	91
		-72	16	-12	30	18	19	92	91
		25	91	15	4	5	-44	-5	91
		26	15	-2	8	18	32	-6	91
		27	14	11	12	1	33	-7	91
		24	-65	59	17	29	31	-4	91
		33	-22	-1	94	-2	-3	-8	91
		91	91	91	91	91	91	91	91

5	semi						-22
		16	-12	30	18	19	71
		91	15	4	5	-44	71
		15	-2	8	18	32	71
		14	11	12	1	33	71
		-65	59	17	29	31	71
		71	71	71	71	71	71

3	mgc				24
		15	4	5	24
		-2	8	18	24
		11	12	1	24
		24	24	24	24

Example 2.46. Let's consider an example of **magic** square of order 11 based on the Result 2.23:

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										275
	-13	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	-162	275
	-5	12	15	39	40	41	42	43	44	-51	55	275
	-6	19	28	72	21	-20	22	23	29	31	56	275
	-7	18	24	16	39	33	18	19	26	32	57	275
	-8	17	25	49	-2	38	39	1	25	33	58	275
	-9	16	26	15	66	25	-16	35	24	34	59	275
	-10	15	27	14	11	12	52	36	23	35	60	275
	-11	14	24	31	11	17	32	34	26	36	61	275
	-12	13	21	-22	29	70	28	27	22	37	62	275
	144	101	35	11	10	9	8	7	6	38	-94	275
	212	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	63	275
	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275	275

The above Example 2.46 is obtained by applying the conditions $R := \frac{11}{9} \times L$, $L := \frac{9}{7} \times T$, $T := \frac{7}{5} \times S$ and $S := \frac{5}{3} \times M$. It includes the following magic squares:

9	mgc	https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT								225
	12	15	39	40	41	42	43	44	-51	225
	19	28	72	21	-20	22	23	29	31	225
	18	24	16	39	33	18	19	26	32	225
	17	25	49	-2	38	39	1	25	33	225
	16	26	15	66	25	-16	35	24	34	225
	15	27	14	11	12	52	36	23	35	225
	14	24	31	11	17	32	34	26	36	225
	13	21	-22	29	70	28	27	22	37	225
	101	35	11	10	9	8	7	6	38	225
	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225	225

2	mgc								175
	28	72	21	-20	22	23	29	175	
	24	16	39	33	18	19	26	175	
	25	49	-2	38	39	1	25	175	
	26	15	66	25	-16	35	24	175	
	27	14	11	12	52	36	23	175	
	24	31	11	17	32	34	26	175	
	21	-22	29	70	28	27	22	175	
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	

5	mgc						125
	16	39	33	18	19	125	
	49	-2	38	39	1	125	
	15	66	25	-16	35	125	
	14	11	12	52	36	125	
	31	11	17	32	34	125	
	125	125	125	125	125	125	

3	mgc				75
	-2	38	39	75	
	66	25	-16	75	
	11	12	52	75	
	75	75	75	75	

3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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